

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES

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REPORT TO

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PREFACE

Nineteen seventy-six marks the twentieth year of operation for the Council on Library Resources (CLR). It seems an appropriate time to review the highlights of the past two decades, to describe current activities in the context of the past, and to relate those activities to the Council's present perception of the development of an improved library system within the United States and abroad.

Because it has no interests to serve other than those of libraries, the Council is in a unique position to view the library world as a whole. The attempt of CLR to discern patterns and trends, to pinpoint library problems through study and research, and to encourage the most promising solutions has, we believe, enabled it to exert some positive influence in library development. The Council has long held the view that many of the needs of libraries and therefore of their users can best be served through the activities of a national library system, composed of cooperating networks of various kinds and drawing upon centralized resources. Because of the flexibility and relative independence it enjoys as a private, operating foundation, the Council has been able to coordinate some of these developments, frequently acting as a mediator or catalyst to ensure that emerging systems will be compatible and contribute to an evolving national system.

At the same time, the Council has attempted to give other important areas of activity the attention they deserve. Programs have been devised and implemented in order to increase the competence and skills of librarians, to assist libraries in better serving their users, and to preserve the collections.

The chapters that follow will perhaps serve to measure how nearly we have met our goals.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

THE YEAR 1975-1976

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THE FIRST FIFTEEN YEARS

The year 1956 was a singular one in the library world. Events typified the conflicting optimism and uncertainty of the mid-fifties -- optimism because of the benefit to libraries to be derived from advances of technology, and a growing recognition of the importance of libraries on a national scale; uncertainty arising from the possibility put forward by some that the new technology would lessen the need for traditional library services, if not, in fact, replace the book.

Great acclaim surrounded Congressional passage on May 8, 1956, of the Library Services Act, the first legislation providing federal money for libraries. Library holdings and services were expanding; book publishers produced more titles (11,480) in the first 11 months of 1956 than in the entire previous year; and the American Library Association's Library Community Project, begun in late 1955, was well on its way toward the goal of determining the proper role of the public library in adult education.

The future of the book was hotly debated at the 20th Annual Conference of the Graduate Library School of the University of Chicago in June 1955 and in the succeeding literature. Indeed, it was chosen the next year as the topic for the seventeenth R. R. Bowker Lecture given at the New York Public Library. While all generally agreed that neither the computer nor microform would actually replace the book, real concern was voiced about the way libraries of the future would deal with the need to provide access to a growing volume of information in all forms. For one thing, accredited library schools produced only 1224 graduates in 1956, a number seen as falling far short of the demand. Computer technology had not yet achieved the capability of handling all the alphabetic characters necessary for bibliographic records. Working in fields

like science, where recorded knowledge was growing at an exponential rate, rising numbers of patrons were creating new demands on and expectations of libraries, which struggled with limited resources to satisfy them.

It is true that some foundation funds were being channeled into libraries, but these were generally earmarked for the erection of buildings and the improvement of local or special collections, thus failing to attack the major sources of difficulty. Although growing production of the paperbound book had reduced the cost of this popular medium to 25¢ per volume, the cost of the hardbound book together with that of cataloging, housing, maintaining, preserving, and circulating it was beginning the rise that would eventually spiral to even greater heights in the sixties and seventies. Confronted with these increasing costs, staff shortages, and outdated buildings and procedures, libraries were falling far short of their own goals, as well as of the expectations of their users. The need for change was apparent; in the words of one commentator, "Perhaps never has the future presented the certainty of so great a change coupled with so great an uncertainty of its direction."

Ford Establishes CLR

This, then, was the climate when, on September 18, 1956, the Ford Foundation announced the establishment of the Council on Library Resources, Inc., with a beginning grant of \$5,000,000. Recognition of the need for a research and development organization was one result of a study begun two years earlier by the Ford Foundation in order to determine the most useful kind of aid the Foundation could provide for libraries. The inquiry culminated in two day-long meetings at the Folger Shakespeare Library, where 50 librarians, scholars, and university administrators considered the problems of libraries and the means for solving them.

On the basis of the recommendations of the Folger group as well as its

own investigation, the Foundation concluded that it could best help libraries through sponsorship of an independent, nonprofit organization, under distinguished leadership, prepared to address itself exclusively to library problems over a suitably long period of time. Free to range widely through research and development in all fields in order to determine new attacks upon the traditional problems involved in the storage and dissemination of knowledge, this organization would accelerate library development by encouraging new methods and helping to coordinate their application. Its most valuable characteristic would be its flexibility; its charge, broad enough to cover any eventuality. It would exist "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of the problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any medium the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership, and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives." Thus the Council on Library Resources came into being, with former Chief Assistant Librarian of Congress Verner W. Clapp as its president.

The problems were great; the funds, limited. From the outset, it was apparent that no organization, no matter how great its resources, could begin to correct the many inadequacies of individual libraries. It therefore became the Council's policy to provide support only for programs that might contribute to solving the problems of libraries in general rather than in specific, local terms. In addition, since all issues could not be attacked simultaneously, the Council developed a kind of priority listing of target areas. With the solution of some problems came the development of new ones, so the Council's concentration of effort has changed with the passing of time. In the 20 years

since the Council's inception -- a period during which annual library and information costs (exclusive of buildings) increased from the millions to the billions -- the Council has received \$29 million in grants from the Ford Foundation.

The Early Years

Out of all the problems facing libraries in the mid-fifties, perhaps the one that caused the greatest concern was the inability to adapt new technologies effectively to the needs of libraries. Indeed, a central conclusion of the Folger conference discussion was "...that libraries, though suffering from all the effects of a machine age, have gained disproportionately little benefit from it; that because libraries do not in many cases provide a market large enough to stimulate the supply of special equipment for their particular needs, many potentially applicable developments in science and technology have not been brought to library tasks."

Thus the Council's first priority seemed clear, and during its first ten years attention was focused primarily "on the exploration of technological means to solve problems that confront libraries in their service to scholarship and research." Basic research was seen as the key to resolving the problems, as offering a fresh look at "the processes of distribution, organization, storage, and communication of knowledge as these affect libraries." Accordingly, the Council launched its effort by probing into the three areas that seemed most crucial to the library's capability of providing information to a reader: bibliographic access, physical access, and administrative arrangements.

Bibliographic Access to Information

The Council's desire to improve the means of bibliographic access, defined as "the devices, arrangements, and forms of organization through which the existence of a source of recorded information is known, together with the location from which it may be procured or at which it may be consulted,"

led to several remarkable achievements in the first decade. They included support for certain bibliographic tools of national significance, such as the third edition of the Union List of Serials, the National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections, a Library of Congress classification scheme for Anglo-American law materials, Choice (a current book selection guide for college and university libraries), and a National Register of Microform Masters. Each of these publications allowed librarians throughout the United States to guide patrons to requested resources more easily and more quickly than ever before.

Several seminal studies in the application of computer technology to bibliographic processes were undertaken. The National Library of Medicine (NLM) received the first grant for this purpose when, in 1958, it sought to improve through mechanization the production of its Current List of Medical Literature, then the world's largest service (in terms of quantity of material indexed) for the literature of a special subject. Retitled Index Medicus, the resulting publication grew eventually into MEDLARS (Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System), one of the best known computer-supported systems of the present day, now utilized by medical researchers all across the country and the world.

Another early grant went to the Library of Congress (LC) for a study to determine the feasibility of applying automated techniques to LC operations. Following the 1963 publication of Automation and the Library of Congress, a second, more finite, study was commissioned, this time dealing with possible methods of converting the data printed on LC catalog cards to machine-readable form. A conversion of this sort would enable the Library to supply these records, on magnetic tape, to many libraries where they could be used to support the production of such widely used items as catalog cards, book catalogs,

and bibliographies. The two reports, along with several conferences, signaled the onset of the Library of Congress' move toward automation of its systems and the construction of an automated national data base.

Projects involving the use of computer techniques to improve access to legal materials, the development of cataloging rules for books in exotic languages, and the first steps toward achieving international agreements on basic cataloging rules were also a part of the Council's initial endeavors.

A different kind of effort to improve bibliographic access took place during those early years. In 1958-59, LC and a group of publishers were supported by CLR in a cooperative experiment to print cataloging information in the book itself. Although the "cataloging-in-source" project was discontinued because of cost factors and technical problems, it provided valuable experience upon which a successful attempt was built over a decade later.

Physical Access to Information

No less important was the Council's involvement in the improvement of physical access to library resources, "the devices, arrangements, and forms of organization through which a source of recorded information...is put into an inquirer's hand." Investigations into the means for increasing library use of photocopies and microforms, the preservation of library and archival materials, the development of mechanical devices to aid in library research, and making research materials available to American scholars were pursued vigorously. One of the Council's first grants in this area went to William J. Barrow, an expert in the history and technology of inks and papers and in document preservation, for systematic research into the causes of paper deterioration and how it could be economically halted or delayed. Subsequent investigations by Barrow and the staff of the W. J. Barrow Laboratory, Inc., established in 1961, resulted in specifications for permanent

and durable paper, now commercially available from several mills. Other studies carried out by Barrow during the first decade of Council support concerned the physical characteristics of catalog cards, book-binding adhesives, and performance standards for library bindings.

The Council has always been concerned with the need for reducing unit costs of library operations. From the first, one of the most alluring possibilities for this was through the use of microforms, both for preservation of deteriorating resources and as a means of low-cost publication and storage. In the late 1950s and early 1960s, the Council moved on many fronts to overcome the shortcomings of microfilm, at that time the most prevalent type of microform used. Attention centered on the equipment used to read microfilm, but it soon became apparent that some of its limitations were only partially amenable to remedy. For example, the Council conducted a concentrated research and development effort aimed at producing an inexpensive, hand-held viewing device that would allow readers to use microfilm almost as easily and pleasurably as books. In the end, none of the readers produced was completely satisfactory. However, each effort added something to the store of knowledge from which later equipment designers worked.

The Council also funded several attempts to develop prototype microcopying equipment, such as a microfiche camera and an automatic book cradle/page turner, along with a low-cost microfilm reader-printer and a high-density, direct-access photo storage and retrieval system. The latter consisted of an electromechanical device that could store a million pages in microform in a cubic foot of space and could find and display or reenlarge any one of them in seconds. Because it could serve only one user at a time, it proved to be too expensive for practical application.

The development of prototype equipment was one approach to the problem of

adapting microform technology successfully to library functions. Another area of interest was the possible benefit offered by microforms in making research materials more readily available to the user. One of CLR's early grants was for experimental micropublication of a scientific journal. A 1961 study on the bibliographical control of microforms, sponsored by the Association of Research Libraries and supported by the Council, led to a revision of the rules for cataloging microforms. This opened the way to other developments, including the establishment in 1965 at the Library of Congress of the National Register of Microform Masters. This publication provides a central source of information on the existence and location of masters from which duplicates can be made. Further, to help librarians deal with the growing amount of equipment associated with microforms, the Council subsidized the first edition of the National Microfilm Association's Guide to Microreproduction Equipment, which has long since become self-supporting.

The Council also pursued the development of other kinds of equipment and processes for copying and reproducing documents. The need for an economical means to duplicate catalog cards caused the Council eight times in the early years to attempt the development of prototype equipment for this purpose. Generally the prototypes produced met some but not all of the needs. Two attempts to develop cameras that would allow scholars to record pages quickly and easily from books in libraries lacking copying machines were not completely satisfactory. Several explorations in the use of television and telefacsimile transmission were also undertaken. While much was learned from each attempt, technical difficulties combined in some cases with high costs to preclude widespread adoption of the equipment by libraries.

Perhaps the most important and long-lasting effort of the Council in dealing with the problem of physical access was its support of the services provided by

the Library Technology Program. After assisting the American Library Association (ALA) with a feasibility study, CLR made a grant in 1958 for the establishment of an ALA unit called the Library Technology Project (LTP). The project's purpose was to collect and disseminate to the library profession information and guidance concerning the use of modern techniques and machines in libraries and to act as a focal point where the interests of librarians, research scientists, and manufacturers could converge.

Projects undertaken by LTP have been as numerous and varied as the needs of libraries, ranging from the investigation of book-truck casters to an examination of carpet underlays. The emphasis has been on the practical, providing information about the things that consume a large share of the library budget -- chairs, desks, photocopy machines, electric typewriters, shelving, and the like. Besides testing commercially available products, LTP has itself sponsored and guided the development of needed new equipment, such as the Se-Lin labeling system which produces long-lasting, tight-sticking labels and applies them to the spines of books.

In addition to books on many aspects of library technology, LTP began in 1965 to issue Library Technology Reports (LTR), a loose-leaf publication containing the results of LTP testing programs. Appearing now as a bound quarterly with an annual microform cumulation, Library Technology Reports continues to provide authoritative consumer information on library equipment, systems, and supplies.

The development of the Library Technology Project illustrates one of the Council's most important procedural principles. It is the Council's view that its grants will most benefit all libraries if they are used as developmental funds for projects that either will become self-supporting or will continue with support from a parent organization. Thus, CLR grants (nearly \$2 million

in 12 years) encouraged ALA to establish and maintain the LTP in order to fill the need for a central source of technical information upon which all libraries could draw. By 1966, less than half its support came from the Council; in 1971, Council funds were no longer required for general operating expenses, although grants are still occasionally made for specific projects.

Administrative Arrangements

Administrative arrangements in libraries, including such elements as the design of a building, the training and organization of staff, development of sources of financial support, etc., made up the third major category of grants during the Council's first ten years. Studies of possible cooperative acquisition arrangements among the libraries in Arkansas, the Rocky Mountain region, and the state of Maine were undertaken during this period. A CLR-funded study of federal libraries led to the establishment in 1965 of the government-wide Federal Library Committee. Handbooks of accepted practice for the gathering and presentation of library statistics, of data processing, and on planning academic and research library buildings were published with Council help. Further, CLR support led to the publication of the 1,559-page second edition of American Library Laws. Proceeds from its sale made possible the publication of a later edition and supplements, which in turn have supported the issuance of updated volumes. The most recent product of this revolving fund is the first supplement to the fourth edition.

Two major surveys had far-reaching results. In cooperation with the American Library Association, the Council supported a Small Libraries Project, designed to tailor new administrative practices and techniques to the needs of libraries serving communities of 10,000 or fewer persons. ALA issued a series of 16 manuals that were subsequently used by most of the small libraries in the United States and Canada. In 1962, a survey of state archival programs began.

The published report, entitled American State Archives, appeared in 1965 and was credited with having an immediate catalytic effect on the development of new state archival programs and the improved organization, administration, and funding of others.

At the conclusion of its first ten years, the Council undertook a summary of its endeavors and in its 10th Annual Report listed both projects and resulting publications. Approximately \$8.5 million had been expended for 346 grants. With the publishing of the King report on automating the Library of Congress, the goal of adapting the techniques of automation to library use seemed well within reach. Progress toward this goal had been demonstrated to the world at the Century 21 International Exposition (Seattle, 1962) and the New York World's Fair (1964-65), where exhibits of libraries containing automated features were displayed. These had been arranged by the American Library Association and sponsored in part by CLR.

The Transitional Years

A shift in priorities took place during the opening years of the Council's second decade, resulting from a combination of factors. It had become clear that the size of investment necessary to develop marketable equipment was beyond the capacity of an organization with limited funds and unlimited responsibilities to libraries. Fortunately, at about this time commercial enterprises became interested in the potential market provided by libraries, particularly in the area of microforms, and began research and development projects of their own. The Council could now shift its attention and energies to other needs. The predicted exponential growth of research libraries had turned these institutions into large bureaucracies with budgets in the millions, thereby creating an urgent need for stronger management skills on the part of administrators. Changing patterns of library use occasioned by the growth of urban areas and the

militancy of students on campuses (who often singled out the library as the target of physical assaults), focused attention on the need to apply critical and creative thinking to the relationship between library and user. New patterns of education predicated on concepts of independent learning over a lifetime began to enlarge the role of the public library as a people's university. In addition, an important event occurred that opened the door wide to real change: with Council aid the MARC (Machine-Readable Cataloging) pilot project was undertaken by the Library of Congress, providing the breakthrough needed to form the foundation upon which further automation efforts and truly national library services could be built.

Almost from its inception the Council supported the application of computer and related technology to library processes. In addition to the work at the National Library of Medicine cited earlier in this report, the Council funded innovative projects in automatic indexing, searching law by computer, computerized maintenance of serials records, research into the library of the future, computer-controlled typographic composition, optical scanning, and many others. With the development of NLM's MEDLARS, computers acquired the ability to handle bibliographic information since they now could command lower as well as upper case type, diacritics as well as Arabic numerals, and non-Latin as well as Roman characters.

From 1961 to 1968, the Council expended over a quarter of a million dollars to enable LC to develop MARC, a most significant step in library automation. Through the distribution of MARC magnetic tapes containing official LC cataloging data, libraries even at great distances could cut costs in two ways: first, by reducing even further the amount of original cataloging, much of it duplicating LC's work, that had formerly been required; second, by using the MARC tapes in local computer facilities to produce catalog cards, book catalogs, reading lists,

etc. The structure of the MARC format was accepted as a national and international standard, in 1971 by the American National Standards Institute and in 1973 by the International Standards Organization. Thus MARC could provide what had heretofore been lacking, a standard method for the transmission of bibliographic data on magnetic tape.

With the development of the MARC format came an abundance of activity in the field of automation. For the first time it was possible to think in terms of the cooperative creation of a national data base, one that could be shared by libraries across the U.S. The way that sharing should be organized became an almost immediate concern, for machine-readable bibliographic data bases began to develop independently and almost simultaneously throughout the country, with little or no official guidance.

The first steps toward a national data base evolved from MARC and were properly taken at the Library of Congress, again with Council initiative and assistance. While MARC was beginning to build a data base of current English language monographs cataloged after the system was created, the data base could not be regarded as complete unless it included records for books in other languages and for books cataloged prior to MARC's appearance. Accordingly, in 1969 LC embarked on a pilot project to experiment with the conversion of those earlier, or retrospective, titles to machine-readable form. Entitled RECON (Retrospective Conversion of Catalog Records), the project was supported by CLR, with additional funding from LC and the Office of Education. RECON demonstrated the technical feasibility and established the unit costs of various approaches to a full-scale retrospective conversion project at the Library of Congress. Unfortunately, the Library concluded that large-scale conversion would be too costly in terms of staff, space, and funds to undertake without massive outside support, and the project was discontinued. The published results

of the pilot project have been useful, however, as other agencies began to convert their records to machine-readable form.

A National Serials Program

At the same time work started on the development of a coordinated national approach to the control of serials, generally defined as those items published on a regular, continuing basis in numbered volumes and issues. After some preliminary work, in 1969 a pilot project was initiated at the Library of Congress for the purpose of experimenting with machine-readable bibliographic data on selected serials held by the three national libraries (Library of Congress, National Library of Medicine, and National Agricultural Library) in order to learn as much as possible about the problems involved, to build files, and to establish techniques and procedures under which a national serials program could be built. The Association of Research Libraries was designated the executive agent for the project, under the aegis of a National Libraries Task Force, which included on its staff two Council employees. With the successful conclusion of the pilot project, in 1972 the National Serials Data Program was established in the Library of Congress.

Essential to the development of a coherent national serials program was the requirement that each title be uniquely identified, in this case by a single number, so that no matter how often a journal changed its title, for example, a user would still be able to retrieve the appropriate bibliographic record. To be effective, that number would have to be generally accepted as a standard.

Since standards and standardization are referred to so frequently in this report and, indeed, are so basic to work in automation and national library programs, we repeat here the definition that was included in the Council's

"Webster defines the word standard as 'something established by authority, custom, or general consent as a model, example, or criterion; something set up or established by authority as a rule for the measure of quantity, weight, extent, value, or quality.' In the context of the Council's work in national and international bibliographic control, standardization means the development and adoption of codes, definitions, rules, and procedures, which will permit a common understanding of the format, control elements, and intellectual content of bibliographic records."

The Council had long been involved in efforts to develop standards. In 1961, CLR and the National Science Foundation (NSF) made their first grants in support of Committee Z/39 of the American National Standards Institute (ANSI), the United States group charged with formulating and gaining acceptance of standards needed in library work, documentation, and related publishing practices. Council staff members have served on various of its subcommittees, including the one responsible for developing a U.S. standard for serial numbers (SSN), which was promulgated and accepted in 1970. Work was immediately undertaken toward a similar agreement on the international level.

By 1967, the Council was allocating more of its funds to projects in automation and national library services than to any other program category, a reflection not only of the Council's concern and continuing interest, but of the expense of research and development in the area. Efforts to apply new thinking to computer technology and organization continued, at the Library of Congress and elsewhere. Two studies at LC explored the possibility of automating the files in the Archive of Folk Song and the feasibility of obtaining automated control of thematic map collections. Work on a manual of systems design for librarians was begun and the new Journal of Library Automation received support. CLR made awards for projects on the computer indexing of archival collections and the development of a computer classification scheme for slides. In addition, seven southern California libraries participated in the testing and appraisal of the Library Information System Time-Sharing System (LISTS). The project proved again the complexities of attempting to automate

diverse library systems; at the same time it demonstrated the effectiveness of automation for small and medium libraries who join forces in its use, rather than "going it alone."

Perhaps the most important venture in library cooperation during this period, and the first to explore the application of MARC tapes for the purpose, occurred in New England. In 1966, CLR made the first of a series of grants to the New England Board of Higher Education for its New England Library Information Network (NELINET). By 1970, NELINET had developed the capability of producing, on demand from subscribing libraries, sets of catalog cards (with a local call number option), spine labels, and book pocket labels for books whose titles were included in the MARC tapes.

Project Intrex at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology was another major effort of the transitional years. The goal of the project, which received its funding from the National Science Foundation and others as well as from CLR, was to develop a possible configuration for the technical library of the future. During the five years of grant support, a system was built whereby a researcher, sitting at a cathode ray tube computer terminal some distance from the central computer, could search for material in an augmented catalog. This catalog differed from a conventional one in its breadth of document coverage, depth of information on each entry, and the easy methods searchers could use in retrieving information. Microfiche images of the full text of items listed in the catalog were stored in a central location. With computer assistance, selected items could then be viewed by the researcher on another type of display console, still at the remote location. If he desired to keep a copy, he could command the system to print one in full size.

Although Intrex proved not to be an economically feasible system at that time, it drew together the capabilities of the computer, of television technology,

and of microform technology. In order to demonstrate their application in a library setting, the Council provided additional funds for a model unit in the M.I.T. engineering library, with a variety of techniques available to assist users. Of benefit to academic libraries in general have been the experiments with point-of-use instruction (packaged programs of audiovisual materials to assist the patron in the use of specialized library tools at the point at which he needs to use them) and the publication of "Library Pathfinders," single sheet guides to published information in specific subject areas.

The rapid advance of computer technology also affected other areas of Council concern. For example, in 1956 computers and microfilm were looked to as prime but separate paths to solutions of library problems. Now, recent projects using computer output microfilm (COM) have shown that combining the two technologies can have beneficial results. In the area of management, the need to incorporate computer technology smoothly into library systems has added to the complexities of library administration; it has increased the requirement for highly trained personnel and for a fresh look at the applicability of current management theories to library problems. Also, the computer, while providing new tools for library users, has at the same time highlighted the importance of a new assessment of library services and their organization -- or reorganization. Finally, the impact of computer technology quickly crossed national boundaries to become an equal force in international terms, making it clear that the same requirements exist for standards and compatible systems on an international as on a national basis.

Experience gained by Council staff in monitoring these and other projects enabled the Council in 1970 to present in its 14th Annual Report its first published statement of its perception of the requirements for the development

of a national library system, along with a view of how that development should proceed. This set the pattern and established the Council's enlarged scheme of priorities for the seventies. The new agenda provides a useful organization for a discussion of the Council's current program, which will be viewed in the context of developments of the last six years. During fiscal 1976, 70 projects were active; new grants and fellowships amounting to \$1,151,684 were awarded, and the Council board authorized an additional \$866,955 for Council-administered awards and project costs.

II

AUTOMATION AND NATIONAL LIBRARY SERVICES

CLR's 14th Annual Report projected a utopian world (in library information terms, at least) in which the United States would have "a single national library system wherein the optimal degree of centralization insured the optimal use of resources to provide the best possible services to library clientele." In this world cataloging would be handled at a central source, as would procurement of materials; thus all libraries would receive cataloging records, as well as books and other library materials, in a timely fashion. There would be a single national data base in machine-readable form encompassing all types of library materials and representing the combined holdings of all libraries. Finally, the combined assets of this national system would be freely available to all libraries and their users through a vast coordinated communications network.

National Library Services

The writer recognized the realities of the situation, however, realities which still apply today. Not only are the vast sums of money required for such a system unavailable, but in the U.S. a completely centralized system is not feasible, politically or otherwise. Nevertheless, in 1970 some of the elements that seemed to presage a national library system were evident. For one thing, the development of MARC seemed to point out the way to the growth of a national data base of records for books, or monographs. Work was progressing toward creating a similar data base for serials. Further, as reported earlier, programs fostered by NELINET showed how a regional system could utilize the bibliographic services of a national

center. Movement toward the provision of national library services -- services performed by central sources and available to all libraries in the country -- had clearly begun, and, in the six years since, has seemed to take a quantum leap.

National library services would allow libraries to reduce high technical processing costs by eliminating the need for each library to duplicate the efforts of others, a wasteful procedure in terms of time as well as money. Development of a national data base would allow libraries to draw necessary bibliographic information from a central source without repeating the effort involved in producing it. This data base would be the foundation of a system of national bibliographic control, defined as a coherent effort coordinated at the national level, that would marshal all the nation's complementary resources and capabilities so as to provide comprehensive control over each bibliographic item (book, journal, etc.) and disseminate effectively to the user the products and services made possible by that control.

The Library of Congress, with items in its collections numbering in the millions and both its cataloging data and format accepted as de facto standards, has long been, in the Council's view, the key node in any national system of bibliographic control. The first public indication that the Library saw itself as the logical agency to serve as the national bibliographic center and was ready to assume those functions was at a June 1975 meeting of the Council for Computerized Library Networks (CCLN). "The Library's role," as described then by William J. Welsh, now Deputy Librarian of Congress, "...is to develop and maintain standard bibliographic devices that will promote consistency in decentralized input to a comprehensive national data base."

The first steps toward the creation of the national data base -- the development of MARC and the RECON project, involving the automated control of cataloging records for monographs -- have already been mentioned. The first two phases of work toward formulation of a national serials program, a study and a pilot project at the Library of Congress, were also described earlier in this report.

A National Data Base for Serials

In 1972, the third step in the creation of a national serials program was initiated. With support from the three national libraries and the Council, the National Serials Data Program was made a separate entity within the Library of Congress. Its main goal was to develop a national machine-readable bibliographic data base for serials that would uniquely identify each title, supply important cataloging information to all libraries, and permit the uniform transfer of data on serials.

Because its work was limited to the files of the three national libraries, it soon became apparent that the program could not build a national serials data base fast enough to satisfy requirements of all libraries, especially as to retrospective records. The only solution seemed to be to make use of the resources and efforts of others outside of the government to construct the needed comprehensive data base.

Thus, a cooperative file-building effort was initiated and entitled the Conversion of Serials (CONSER) Project. Recognizing the dual need for a formal entity to administer CONSER and for the management to reside outside of the administrative structure of the participants, the Council agreed to fund and manage CONSER in the initial phases. In December 1974, CLR signed a contract with the Ohio College Library Center (OCLC) for the use

of its computer facilities. The Library of Congress, the National Library of Canada, and the University of Minnesota made their automated serials files available as the initial data base. Nine other libraries currently participate on-line to add new records, upgrade old ones, and correct others in the basic file. It is projected that this integrated, cooperative file will eventually contain from 200,000 to 300,000 serial records. As of June 1976, it held more than 125,000 such records.

Two CLR systems specialists have worked full time on the CONSER Project since it began nearly three years ago. On November 21, 1975, CLR made a grant to the Library of Congress to support the systems design and programming required to integrate the functions of the CONSER Project with the other technical processing activities managed by LC. The Library plans to assume responsibility for the management and permanent maintenance of the data base and for distribution of resulting products by November 1977.

At the end of June 1976, the first part of the project study was completed. It describes the services LC must provide in order to assume responsibility for the data base in the short term, and to operate a serials program nationwide in the long term. The principal emphasis of the second part of the study will be on manpower requirements and the necessary steps for implementation of the program. The finished report will deal with the Library of Congress' implementation of the CONSER Project and, more important, its place in a comprehensive national serials system, an integral element of national bibliographic control.

Included in the initial CONSER data base are serial titles in the field of the humanities, processed by LC National Serials Data Program staff. This segment of the project is supported by matching grants from the Council and

the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH). A parallel effort to accelerate the availability of serial records in science and technology is supported by the National Science Foundation. The science and technology part of the project involves participation by the National Federation of Abstracting and Indexing Services, an important first step in cooperative data base building across professional lines.

A National Data Base for Monographs

The management of a national serials system represents, however, only one function of the Library of Congress as the national bibliographic center. In 1974 the Library launched, with CLR support, three other positive steps toward the development of its national bibliographic service.

Under the first program, designated the Cooperative MARC (COMARC) pilot project, LC utilizes machine-readable records, created locally by selected libraries throughout the U.S. and based on LC cataloging copy derived from cards, proof sheets, and entries in the National Union Catalog. With the help of the Council's grant, the Library accepts these records from authorized participants, removes the duplicates, compares the records with the official catalog, updates them for consistency when required, and redistributes them through the MARC Distribution Service. This broadens the scope of LC's MARC coverage of books and, if successful, will demonstrate that quality and consistency can be maintained in a data base even if a number of institutions contribute to it (decentralized input), as long as one institution is responsible for checking the contributed records and changing them if necessary (central bibliographic authority). This concept is critical to the early establishment of a national bibliographic data base.

During the past year, the Washington State Library, Information Dynamics Corporation, the University of Chicago, Boston Theological Institute, Cornell University Library, and Northwestern University Library were selected to participate in the COMARC project. They were chosen on the basis of the completeness of the data content of their records and their adherence to MARC encoding. The first COMARC records were made available through the MARC Distribution Service with the subscription year that began on April 1, 1976.

For the second endeavor, CLR funds allowed the Library to contract with an outside consultant who, together with LC staff, conducted a study of the requirements for the design and implementation of a Core Bibliographic System. The results of the study, which took into account the Library's internal processing requirements as well as those necessary for its projected national bibliographic service, will provide part of the blueprint for the hardware and software systems the Library will need.

The third aspect of the three-phased project was an attempt to develop a machine-readable format for libraries to use when reporting their holdings to the National Union Catalog. The format would be based on the MARC record for each title but would contain fewer data elements, in the hope that the information could be made available to users more quickly than is possible at present. A report has been prepared and its implications are presently being studied by the Library of Congress.

When completed, LC's national bibliographic service will include an expanded MARC Distribution Service, on-line access to bibliographic records for all forms of material, on-line access to name and subject authority files, and on-line access to the National Union Catalog location file.

In other words, when the service becomes fully operational, libraries needing bibliographic information from LC will be able to retrieve it using a computer terminal, probably via a regional network tied directly into the LC computer system.

It will be some years before all libraries are able to tap into automated bibliographic resources, yet the need to catalog materials quickly and accurately is ever pressing. In this connection, a different kind of program at the Library of Congress, supported by the Council joined by the National Endowment for the Humanities, has already produced cost benefits for libraries of all types. The goal of the Cataloging-in-Publication (CIP) program, first attempted in the late 1950s and revived ten years later, is to make LC cataloging information available more quickly to all who purchase books. Drawing upon the results of the experiment referred to earlier, project planners reevaluated the cost factors and resolved the technical problems. Now over 1100 publishers submit books in the galley stage to the Library of Congress so that cataloging data can be prepared and subsequently printed in the book itself. Over 82,000 titles have been processed since July 1971 when the program was put into operation. Cost reduction benefits for libraries result from the fact that the book no longer has to be cataloged separately by those libraries that cannot afford either MARC tapes or the time of professional librarians. Further, the cataloging data is immediately available for use, eliminating the time lag between receipt of the book and the arrival of LC catalog cards or MARC tapes, time when the book was usually unavailable for use by library clientele.

Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control

The Library of Congress is not, of course, working in a vacuum; indeed it represents only one, albeit an important one, of the institutions concerned with the development of a national system for handling information. Abstracting and indexing services, publishers, book dealers, and other professionals share a concern for the way in which such a system may be constructed. In April 1974, at a meeting sponsored jointly by the National Science Foundation and the Council on Library Resources, 45 participants representing various sectors of the information community met to design "programs of action," that would "constitute some of the building blocks of the improved national bibliographic system." One outgrowth of that meeting was the appointment of a Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control (CCNBC), supported by CLR, NSF, and the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science (NCLIS). The Council agreed to administer the funds for the committee, maintain the files, handle correspondence, and implement the committee's decisions.

The committee members were given eight specific charges at the initial planning meeting:

1. Define the minimum bibliographic record required for item identification;
2. Study the requirement for additional standards in the fields of libraries, documentation, and related publishing practices, and recommend action to the proper agency;
3. Promote the interchange of bibliographic records among libraries, systems, and across professional lines;
4. Devise record formats and content designation schemes for journal articles, technical reports, and other forms of literature not presently covered by the MARC formats;
5. Study the problem of coupling noncharacter representations, such as graphics or numerical data, to the related bibliographic records;

6. Promote improved bibliographic access across professional lines;
7. Devise a national bibliographic name authority system; and
8. Study the problem of subject access and make recommendations aimed at solutions.

CCNBC has thus far devised four different approaches to carry out its task. It appoints working parties to deal with particular problems, commissions studies, holds planning meetings on specific subjects, and recommends formal standards activity.

Two working parties were appointed last year to prepare a detailed analysis of their assigned areas and to recommend needed action. The Working Party on Formats for Journal Articles and Technical Reports and the Working Party on Bibliographic Name Authority Files held their first meetings in July and August of 1975 and have continued to meet on a quarterly basis. By the end of June 1976, each group reported progress toward developing formats that may result in accepted standards in their respective areas.

The complexity of issues surrounding the possible use of bar codes on books called for a different kind of approach -- initiation of a series of meetings to examine the problem and to determine how it might best be investigated.

Bar codes are vertical lines representing coded numbers and/or letters that can be read by automated devices called optical scanners. An example of this is the Universal Product Code (UPC), used primarily for items on sale in supermarkets. The UPC translates product identification numbers into a form that can be easily and quickly read by optical scanners located at a supermarket's checkout counters. Its purpose, with the aid of a computer, is to automate customer sales transactions and capture individual

product data. The code can be used for product control by manufacturers, distributors, wholesalers, retailers -- in short, by everyone who handles the item from the time it is packaged until a consumer carries it out of the supermarket door.

In recent months, book jobbers and vendors have become interested in having publishers print bar codes (or some other form of optical code) on books and magazines, so that they may also be handled automatically. To determine how the bar code issue could best be examined, CCNBC called a meeting in May 1976 to which representatives of the library community, book vendors, and publishers were invited. Following the recommendation of that group, the committee plans to hold another meeting, this time to include representatives of various bar code encoding schemes, equipment vendors, abstracting and indexing services, etc., at which discussion will center on the possible effects of the use of bar codes on the library and associated information communities.

Another number used for the control of books, especially by publishers for processing book orders, is the International Standard Book Number (ISBN). Whether this number also can be used effectively by libraries, other than for ordering books, is the subject of a study being conducted for CCNBC by Helen Schmierer of the University of Chicago Library. Commissioning such a study is the third approach used by the committee.

The fourth approach concerns the area of standards. When committee discussion results in a matter that seems to require the preparation of a formal standard, the problem is forwarded to the appropriate agency for consideration. An example of this is the matter of holdings statements for serials. A serial holdings statement is the information in a bibliographic record that tells how many years or volumes of a particular periodical are

contained in the collections of a library, consortium, or other institution. The problem of how much information is needed in a computerized record to describe adequately the holding and how it should be displayed arose out of work on the CONSER Project. The committee felt discussion of the problem had proceeded to the point where a subcommittee of the American National Standards Institute's (ANSI) Committee Z/39 (responsible for standards in the area of libraries, documentation, and related publishing practices) should attempt to define a standard for that part of the serial record containing a holdings statement. The chairman of the Z/39 Committee accepted the charge and during the past year set up a subcommittee (Z/39.40) to prepare a standard format for serial holdings statements.

Network Development

The value to libraries of cooperative endeavors has been proved many times over in the last 20 years. When the Council was established, the acquisition of library materials seemed to represent the most pressing requirement for coordinated action on the local and state level. As stated earlier, the Council in the early 1960s took part in efforts to establish several state and regional cooperative library systems. The need for cooperative action became even more pressing with the advent of automation, for applying technology to manual systems has proved to be initially an expensive proposition. Except for a few of the largest institutions, the way that most libraries have been able to take advantage of automated procedures is through the forming of various kinds of consortia.

In the last six years, the growth of library networks has accelerated, each one incorporating to some degree three essential characteristics: the network exists to marshal resources and accomplish results beyond the ability

of any one of its members; it has established a clearly identifiable domain based on its organizational design and structure; it utilizes some form of communications technology. Despite these similarities, the growth has not been the result of a coordinated national effort, nor has national leadership emerged to insure that the vision of a flexible confederation of library systems working toward an ideal national system will become a reality.

In a modest way, the Council has attempted to fill that gap. One method, of course, is in the selection of programs to support. An equally important though less formal influence is in the advice, evaluation, and assistance provided on demand by CLR systems specialists who attempt to prevent wasteful duplication of effort and to promote a rational division of labor. To encourage coordination of efforts, the Council may use a third mechanism, that of providing an opportunity for network proponents to talk directly with each other and discuss their mutual concerns. To this end, the Council sponsored an April 1976 meeting, at the Library of Congress, of major network directors. A second meeting is scheduled for late summer.

In choosing programs for support, the Council attempts to focus on those that appear to offer solutions to current library problems and to apply automation theories knowledgeably in support of day-to-day operations. Other criteria used to evaluate proposals include how well they fit the overall pattern of national development, whether they have the enthusiastic support of the sponsoring institution and a commitment for continued funding upon reaching operational status, and whether they are sound in concept and realistic as to schedule. Another most important consideration is the expertise and experience of the proponents themselves.

Two regional cooperative efforts, for which Council support has now ended, took place in New England (NELINET) and in the Southwest. Here a project involving the state librarians and library associations of Texas, Louisiana, Arkansas, Oklahoma, Arizona, and New Mexico, resulted in the 1971 establishment of the Southwestern Library Interstate Cooperative Endeavor (SLICE). Council funds enabled SLICE to staff an office for its first four years, during which a systematic regional plan was developed for increasing and stimulating the sharing of library resources, services, and expertise within the region. Specific projects undertaken by SLICE included extending MARC-based services to members, initiating programs of continuing education, and preparing studies on such topics as the legal and contractual aspects of establishing a multi-state network, the use of telecommunications in library networks, and computer-based data processing.

The Ohio College Library Center

Perhaps the best known bibliographic network emanates from the Ohio College Library Center (OCLC), located in Columbus, Ohio. OCLC began as an operating system for Ohio libraries in the early 1970s and now serves some 800 libraries throughout the nation. Its automated bibliographic data base, combining records from MARC tapes with those introduced locally by members, contains over 2.3 million entries. One of its most valuable services is the provision of catalog cards to members, now produced at the annual rate of 60 million.

OCLC's early developmental aspects had been funded by the U.S. Office of Education and by participating Ohio libraries. CLR began to share these costs with a small grant made in 1970; by 1973, new and substantially increased developmental funds were being provided by the Council. By 1975,

the first of OCLC's six long-range designs for its on-line system -- an on-line union catalog with shared cataloging capability -- had become fully operational. The use of OCLC's computer facility to create a national serials data base under terms of the CONSER Project is helping the center progress toward its second long-term goal: serials control. The other projected elements, some of which are being developed with grants from other funding agencies, include capabilities for control of acquisitions, interlibrary loan communication, remote catalog access, circulation control, and subject retrieval.

OCLC received a fourth CLR grant in May 1975, for the development of acquisitions and authority file subsystems and for installing a subject retrieval capability by contracting with the Battelle Memorial Institute for use of its search system (BASIS).

An acquisitions subsystem would support the acquisition of new materials by OCLC member libraries by first allowing an on-line search to determine whether the desired item is already on hand or on order. It would then automatically prepare order forms, process invoices, issue claims for orders not received, and account for funds. An authority file subsystem would enhance the quality of the on-line catalog by providing, for example, the authoritative form of authors' names, together with cross-references to other versions of the names, thus allowing for ready identification of a particular author. Utilization of the BASIS system would enlarge the search capability of the catalog, since it allows for free-text searching on words contained in bibliographic records in addition to those designated as subject terms.

At the end of June, a study of the utility of authority file subsystems was nearing completion, along with implementation of the BASIS system. Work is under way on the claims component of the acquisitions subsystem.

The importance of OCLC lies in its successful demonstration that cathode ray tube terminals, telephone lines, and computers can be combined to produce an on-line system that will effectively support library functions. Developments pioneered at OCLC have heavily influenced similar efforts elsewhere. In 1972, OCLC and NELINET obtained CLR funds to determine the feasibility of replicating OCLC's data base on a regional basis. Although the project proved technically feasible, NELINET decided instead to join OCLC as a regional member. Other consortia, such as PALINET (Pennsylvania Area Library Network), the Consortium of Universities in the District of Columbia, and SOLINET (Southeastern Library Network) followed this example to join OCLC's far-flung operation.

Although OCLC has become the largest library network in existence, it has by no means solved all the problems involved in library automation and networking. The Council believes that a variety of approaches must be explored, that the growth of separate but compatible regional networks is a necessary step to the evolution of a national library system. Thus CLR has provided support for several other cooperative programs, some of which seek to attain very specific objectives. For example, in 1973 a small grant to the Washington State Library provided for the development of an on-line acquisitions module to enhance its state-wide computerized bibliographic network.

BALLOTS

Shortly after OCLC opened its doors to Ohio libraries, a second pioneering on-line system went into production at Stanford University in California.

Entitled BALLOTS (Bibliographic Automation of Large Library Operations Using a Time-sharing System), the system's support came initially from the U.S. Office of Education and has been continued with funds from the Council and the National Endowment for the Humanities. Its primary function is to assist the technical processing activities of the Stanford University Libraries, and, by extension, to support and improve services in other California libraries. MARC records form a major portion of the BALLOTS data base, which also contains records of titles being acquired and cataloged by Stanford. Together with assistance in cataloging and serials maintenance, the system now supports the ordering, claiming, canceling, receiving, and in-process control of material received on approval or under blanket order plans, on regular or standing order, by exchange, or as gifts.

In 1975, additional funds from CLR and NEH enabled BALLOTS to undertake the development of a new complete MARC-character-set video terminal and to improve the design of the file in order to make the system more readily usable as a network by interested libraries. At about the same time, seven California public libraries, members of PLAN (Public Library Automation Network), started to use the BALLOTS cataloging system. Now other public, academic, research, special, state, and federal libraries have begun to use specific support functions of the system.

Users have the option of viewing data a line at a time or by the screenful (full-face mode). This flexibility permits different hookup arrangements with the system and therefore different cost arrangements. In June 1976, it was announced that the BALLOTS system could now handle a complete MARC record in the full-face mode; the first user of this mode outside of Stanford will be the University of California at Berkeley. At the same time, the BALLOTS Center announced that it could provide its members with catalog cards,

presorted and ready for filing into a library's catalog. And by September 1976, subscribing libraries will be able to store on-line their locally produced catalog records, update their own records, and review or copy records contributed by other local libraries.

Southeastern Library Network

Council support for another regional network, the Southeastern Library Network (SOLINET), ended this year. SOLINET's principal outside support comes from the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation. The ten-state cooperative was organized following the expansion of OCLC's services to regional groups outside of Ohio. Instead of replicating the OCLC system, however, SOLINET has coordinated an effort to place OCLC terminals in its members' libraries, thus allowing them to utilize the OCLC data base directly. A CLR staff member was asked to consult with the group prior to its incorporation; a small CLR grant was awarded in 1974 toward a training program for librarians participating in the network. In May 1976, SOLINET published a terminal training manual consisting of a workbook and audiotape kit of instruction to assist new operators in the use of the OCLC 100 computer terminal. It is believed that the manual will find wide utility among OCLC users in other networks.

WICHE

Last year, the Council made a grant to the Western Interstate Commission for Higher Education (WICHE) for design and developmental work leading to a Western Interstate Bibliographic Network. Work on this grant has been delayed because of a reorganization of the library program within WICHE, which is responsible for over 50 programs related to the needs of higher education in the West. In April 1976, the name of WICHE's library program, formerly the Western Network, was changed to the Western Interstate Library

Coordinating Organization (WILCO), with the states of Alaska, Arizona, California, Idaho, Montana, Nevada, Oregon, South Dakota, and Washington as members. WILCO now operates under the direction of the Western Council of State Librarians. At the end of June, WILCO personnel were beginning to explore the ways in which the coordination of current bibliographic and resource-sharing activities in the western states could be improved.

Library Data Management System

The library networks mentioned thus far in this report support the activities of small to medium-sized libraries. Although BALLOTS was designed primarily to serve the needs of Stanford's large research library, its designers planned from the beginning to extend its services via networking to smaller libraries in the Bay area. Large research libraries have problems of a different, and perhaps more difficult, nature. Often the computer facilities on campus must be shared between the library and other general university management needs. Software development for library support must mesh smoothly with those systems serving other campus offices. In order to explore these problems, in 1970 the Council and NEH made a joint five-year grant for the further development of the University of Chicago's projected Library Data Management System.

By 1973, the overall design of the system was virtually complete. Commercial software packages had been acquired and adapted to handle both library and campus administrative applications. The system design includes a single integrated data file to be stored in the university's central IBM 370/168 computer which is accessible to the library through a Varian mini-computer. In 1975, CLR awarded a new grant to the University of Chicago for continued development of the system, this time to include an examination of how it could be made available to other libraries.

At the end of June, the university library reported that it was preparing to initiate testing of a pilot circulation system. By January 1977, it is projected that the general circulation system will be fully operational and the existing manual system will be closed. Other manual systems, such as the in-process order file, may be closed in the near future. The data management system is already providing heavy support to the library's acquisitions and cataloging units, with approximately 150,000 titles now accessible on-line. A number of public demonstrations have shown that the University of Chicago's Data Management System functions now as an integral part of the day-to-day activities of the Joseph Regenstein Library.

Other Automation Projects

Council support for automation projects has not been limited to large libraries or networks. Funds have been provided for smaller automation projects when they show promise and contribute to the overall development of computer application to library use. In the early 1970s, for example, a small grant enabled Bucknell University to experiment with a program that allowed students to retrieve information from a central bibliographic data base using remote terminals; another project goal was the development of a model subject search capability. Later, the Ohio State University Library conducted a statistical study of transaction activity in their large on-line automated circulation system.

Four new grants this year paved the way for additional applications of automation to library processes and associated activities. Early in the year, CLR made a grant to the American Society for Information Science (ASIS) toward preparation of a 25-year cumulative index of the journal of the society, JASIS. Published in early 1976, the Cumulative Index

provides a "core collection" of information science periodical literature that appeared in the magazine from 1950 to 1974. The project utilized generally accepted indexing terminology and standards in such a way as to provide a model for the profession as a whole. As a condition of the grant, ASIS agreed that a percentage of any profits from sales would be earmarked for future updates.

Increasing the accessibility of legal materials was the subject of a two-day conference of law librarians, legal editors, computer experts, and attorneys held in Concord, New Hampshire, in April 1976. The PTC Research Foundation of the Franklin Pierce Law Center sponsored the event, which was partially supported with a small CLR grant. Entitled "Computer Access to Secondary Legal Materials," the conference's goal was to develop a uniform method of abstracting articles in legal periodicals for computer storage and retrieval. The data bank thus produced would complement current computerized programs (LEXIS, Auto-Cit, AcCIS), which handle only case law, statutes, and congressional documents. Proceedings of the conference are to be published in issue no. 3 of IDEA, a quarterly law journal published by the center.

Improving on-line accessibility to bibliographic records contained in computerized data bases is the ultimate goal of two new projects receiving CLR awards. The library of the University of Illinois College of Law plans to program and evaluate a computer on-line reference service for library users, particularly valuable when professional help is not available in the library, for instance at night or on weekends. Utilizing the university's on-line computer system, PLATO (Programmed Logic for Automation Teaching Operation), the law library will initiate a pilot project that concentrates on its collection of state and federal documents. The project uses the unique

graphic capabilities of PLATO to provide direction to the user, a service he would normally get from a reference librarian.

That subject access to monographs can be improved by augmentation of MARC records is the premise of an experiment to be carried out by the Syracuse University School of Information Studies with the help of a CLR grant. Working with a sample of books drawn from the collections of the University of Toronto comprising a number of subject categories in the humanities and social sciences, the project staff will add subject terms to those already contained in the MARC record of each book. The new terms will consist of descriptive words and phrases chosen according to a set of selection rules from the index and/or table of contents. The file of records for the books in the sample will be processed by the System Development Corporation's ORBIT Search Service. Computer-based subject searches can then be made by project staff and others who have access to the service. If this method proves feasible and cost effective, one hoped-for result may be that book indexers and publishers will take greater care in preparing indexes, knowing that their efforts will be utilized for on-line searching.

The Need for Standards

Progress in librarianship has always been facilitated by the development of acceptable standards. Witness, for example, the use of the 3" x 5" catalog card; its general adoption meant that a central source could manufacture and distribute cards for catalogs located anywhere, thus reducing costs of individual production. Standardization is even more important in the development of bibliographic information. With standardization, the exchange of bibliographic information between libraries is facilitated, as is its use in constructing tools that can be easily understood by all libraries

and their users. Standardization also ensures and enhances the quality of all professional library products and services. In the work toward achieving national and international bibliographic control, particularly with the advent of automation, the need for acceptable standards has increased. If it is to be possible for libraries to exchange information about their holdings, to share the task of constructing data bases, or to work together in consortia and networks, there must be absolute agreements on the conventions that govern library processes.

The Council has for many years pressed for the development of standards as a necessary step in the evolution of a national library system. The problem has been attacked on many fronts; an example is the development of standard serial numbers that uniquely identify each individual serial title, no matter how often it changes. CLR staff members working on international committees helped to secure the 1973 adoption of an international standard serial number (ISSN) based on the format for the American standard serial number.

Anglo-American Cataloging Rules

But apart from committee work and the sponsorship of key meetings, the Council has also funded specific projects devoted to the development of standards and the encouragement of their use. In 1975, a grant was made to the American Library Association on behalf of the Joint Steering Committee for the Revision of the Anglo-American Cataloging Rules (AACR), a basic tool for catalogers as well as a powerful force for standardization. Members of the committee include representatives of ALA, the Canadian Committee on Cataloguing, the (British) Library Association, the British Library, and the Library of Congress.

The first edition of the AACR was published in 1967. However, several developments in the intervening years, such as the promulgation of international standards and the inclusion of new kinds of materials (e.g., audiovisuals) in library collections, have mandated a revision. During this year, the committee met several times and also sent members to additional meetings to coordinate their work with other bodies whose interests coincide. The revised edition of the AACR is scheduled for completion within the next two years.

ANSI Committee Z/39

Together with the National Science Foundation, CLR has since 1961 supported the work of Committee Z/39 of the American National Standards Institute (ANSI). A federation of more than 160 technical, professional, and trade organizations and 1,000 companies, ANSI acts as the national clearinghouse and coordinating agency for voluntary standards in the United States. Its Committee Z/39 is responsible for standards in library work, documentation, and related publishing practices. Two new CLR grants, successively covering the period from April 1, 1976, to June 30, 1978, will allow for expansion of Z/39's professional staff, for the development of a national standards information center for standards from any source that come under the committee's purview, and for necessary travel in connection with standards work.

In 1975, three new Z/39 standards, covering technical report numbers, romanization of Hebrew, and advertising of micropublications, were published. In addition, the committee has agreed to administer two subgroups of the International Standards Organization (ISO), of which ANSI is a member; this requires regular and active participation in primary international standards work. The subgroups oversee standards work dealing with character sets and numbering systems in documentation.

To accept standards is not enough; they must also be widely used and adhered to in order for the maximum benefit to be obtained. For example, international standard serial numbers are of most use when they are printed on the front cover of a magazine to provide easy, positive identification when the periodical is received by a library. In 1975, a small grant to the Boston Theological Institute (BTI) assisted in a program of encouraging publishers of theological serials to print assigned ISSNs on the covers of their publications. In an April 1976 report to the Council, the project director wrote that in almost every instance, serials publishers who were approached agreed to print the ISSN either on the front cover or within the publication. The project thus far has demonstrated the usefulness of an aggressive information campaign promoting adoption and use of standards. A supplemental grant made to BTI this past year will allow the institute to complete its project by communicating with publishers of an additional 709 titles.

Programs in the area of automation, networks, standards, and national library services continue to consume a major portion of available Council funds. Grants totaling \$509,213 and allocation of an additional \$25,000 for future activity were made in this category during fiscal 1976.

III

PRESERVATION AND CONSERVATION

MICROGRAPHICS

The program areas covered in this section of the report -- the preservation and conservation of materials and the application of microform technology to library needs -- have been of concern to the Council from the outset. In fact, 40 percent of the funds granted in the first two years of Council operation went to projects intended to deal with these matters.

As time passed, activities in these two areas have appeared in many ways to relate to and complement each other. Since mid-1972, the two have been the province of one program officer with, we believe, benefit to both. His knowledge and awareness of developments in micrographics have hastened and enhanced their application to some of the preservation problems discussed below.

Preservation and Conservation Progress

Although library collections have expanded to include a wide variety of nonprint media (e.g., films, cassette tapes, recordings, and, occasionally, even power tools and appliances), books are still the library's chief stock-in-trade; a concomitant problem, then, remains the deterioration of paper. The Council has approached the problem of deterioration in two ways: first, by supporting research into the causes of deterioration and the methods for halting it and repairing its effects; second, by investigating the potential of transferring information to microforms when the paper on which it appears has disintegrated past the point of salvation, or when the item is too

valuable for general use and circulation or is too costly to maintain in its original format. The peculiar twist to the problem of paper deterioration is that it is not the oldest papers that are most in jeopardy, but rather the newer books and journals that have been printed since the mid-nineteenth century by sophisticated technological processes. Investigation in the deterioration of bookstock was one of the Council's earliest priorities. Although many developments since then have helped to define the problem and successful remedies have been applied, support of preservation activities remains, after 20 years, an important facet of the Council's work.

Several organizations have received support for research into and applications of methods to prevent papers from disintegrating. The Council's first grant in this area was made in 1957 to W. J. Barrow, a documents restorer at the Virginia State Library, to investigate the cause of paper deterioration. Support for Barrow and, following his death, the W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc., has continued to the present day. In addition to Barrow, within the last six years both the Library of Congress Preservation Office and the New England Document Conservation Center have received CLR grants. A 1971 award to the Library of Congress enabled it to purchase equipment for its new Preservation Research Office. Establishment of this office was part of a national preservation plan that resulted from a Council-supported study by the Association of Research Libraries (ARL), the first step of which was a pilot preservation project at LC. This project, also funded by CLR, dealt with procedural problems associated with a scheme to salvage LC's "brittle books." It came to a successful conclusion in 1969. Today the Library's

extensive microfilming program for brittle books is supported by appropriated funds.

In 1973, a two-year CLR grant was made to assist in the establishment of the New England Document Conservation Center, which serves as a restoration center and conservation information clearinghouse for libraries, archives, and related governmental agencies primarily in the six-state New England region. By the end of the grant period, the center was completely self-supporting. As the first regional conservation program, it provides a practical model for applying preservation techniques at this level.

CLR has extended support in recent years for such other preservation and restoration projects as research into the special problems occasioned by flooding of libraries and archives, and the preparation of a manual on conservation. Any discussion of the Council's work in preservation, however, must begin with William J. Barrow to whom must be given the credit for early determining the primary cause of paper deterioration.

In the first half of the century, there was a belief that atmospheric pollution, particularly in urban areas, was the main factor leading to paper deterioration. Barrow disputed this notion and by the late 1950s his experiments led him to conclude that the deterioration was caused primarily by internal, rather than external, agents, namely chlorides from the bleach used in paper manufacture and alum from the size. The use of these chemicals produces highly acidic papers, and this causes deterioration.

Following this discovery, Barrow turned his attention to developing methods of deacidifying the paper in existing books, continuing to use his one- and two-bath processes, which are commonly employed by conservators today. These processes, however, treat individual sheets; application to any substantial number of books requires impracticable amounts of time and labor.

After Barrow's death in 1967, his laboratory staff continued the work, concentrating on methods of deacidifying whole books by impregnating them with a class of compounds called organic amines. Morpholine was chosen as the most suitable of these for further experimentation. The laboratory staff subsequently developed a morpholine vapor deacidification process and related equipment capable of deacidifying five to ten books at a time, for the most part without deleterious side effects.

The National Endowment for the Humanities joined the Council this year in supporting a large-scale test of the morpholine vapor deacidification process, to be undertaken by Barrow laboratory staff in cooperation with the Virginia State Library. A portion of the \$176,000 grant will be used to construct a larger version of the original processor, this one designed to treat 50-100 books simultaneously in 30 minutes or less.

The collections of the Virginia State Library, representing deterioration problems common to many libraries, will be used for the test. The library will also provide operators and space for the processor as well as required utilities. The Council has arranged with Research Corporation, a nonprofit organization, to patent the process. If morpholine vapor deacidification is demonstrated to be practical and safe

for routine use in libraries, Research Corporation will promote the process and license its use. Any profits from the venture will be used for further research.

Permanent/Durable Paper

Problems of preserving deteriorating books and periodicals would be greatly lessened if an acid-free paper were used in the first place. Following his identification of acid as the primary factor in deterioration of paper, W. J. Barrow began to work on specifications for production of a permanent and durable paper that would also be economical to manufacture. Such a paper would be acid-free and also possess characteristics enabling it to resist damage from folding and other hazards of daily use. Success came in 1959 when the Standard Paper Manufacturing Company of Richmond produced five tons of a fine 60-pound book paper, the first paper deliberately manufactured as a strong, stable (permanent) paper for general use at a competitive price. Although permanent/durable paper based on Barrow's specifications and with a useful life of hundreds of years is now commercially available, it regrettably has not been widely used. However, two developments in the past year may be harbingers of an increased interest in ensuring, before publication, that documents will endure, rather than attempting to reverse the degeneration process once it has begun.

In consultation with the American Association of University Presses, the National Historical Publications Commission has issued recommended standards of paper quality for the historical publications that it sponsors. These standards are based primarily on the specifications developed by the W. J. Barrow Laboratory. A second development concerns paper used

for copying purposes. Although many documents are copied for short-term use, others are copied for use in archives, for legal purposes (e.g., wills, contracts), or for original publication (theses, dissertations), where long-term preservation is essential. A major manufacturer of copying machines has now developed an "archival bond" paper to be used in these instances; it was produced according to specifications by the National Bureau of Standards for the National Archives.

In fiscal 1971-72, the Council awarded grants to Anthony Cains, a bookbinder who had been in charge of the restoration activities at the Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale, Florence (BCNF), following the 1966 flood, and to Margaret Hey, an English chemist. Miss Hey's grant supported her investigation at the Istituto di Patologia del Libro in Rome into the effects of various bleaches on paper and her evaluation of heatset paper tissues, a material specially made for mending of paper by dry application and used in Florence on books damaged in the flood. Mr. Cains' grant was to complete preparation of a workshop manual on restoration of water-damaged printed books and parchment manuscripts, describing techniques used by BCNF following the Florence disaster.

Last year, Miss Hey informed the Council that she had returned to England to complete work on the chapters concerning her research that will appear in the Cains manual and to assist in the manual's revision. This year, a contract was signed with the London publishing firm Butterworth & Co., Ltd., for publication of the work.

Micrographics

Council interest in the development and use of microforms stems from more than its desire to find practical, economical methods of preserving paper. Microforms are indeed a second answer to the problem of deteriorating materials, but to this reason for using microforms must be added several others that have become important in recent years.

Since the production of microforms can be substantially less expensive than printing, publishers of scholarly or specialized materials have begun to produce in microform materials that had previously been published in conventional form. Indeed, Literary Marketplace for 1976-77 lists 50 U.S. firms as "micropublishers," those who specialize in this format. Because of the physical space saved by micropublications, small libraries can now provide large collections of material to local users. For example, subscribers to the microfiche collection of the ERIC (Educational Resources Information Center) Document Reproduction Service can obtain each month approximately 800 noncopyrighted educational research documents on about 120 microfiche. The relative ease with which microforms can be produced and their relatively low cost make them particularly useful for publishing materials (catalogs, for example) that must be frequently updated.

The CLR staff member whose specialty is micrographics has for some time functioned in the dual capacity of program officer and consultant. As a program officer, he reviews proposals in the area of preservation and microforms that are submitted to the Council and makes recommendations as to possible funding. He also develops projects

based on perceived needs and administered by the Council, such as the COM project described later. As a consultant, he provides informed and unbiased assistance to libraries interested in microforms at no cost to those he advises and acts generally as a monitor and advocate for them vis-a-vis the industry. He works closely with the National Microfilm Association and with committees and advisory groups of such organizations as the American Library Association, the Association of Research Libraries, the U.S. Office of Education, and Committee Z/39 of the American National Standards Institute. In this latter capacity, he chaired the Z/39 subcommittee that wrote a standard for the advertising of micropublications, approved in 1975 by the ANSI Board of Standards Review. In addition to responding to requests for assistance, he is frequently involved in microform seminars, panel discussions, and review activities. He is also the editor, and sometime contributor, of a series of columns in ALA's American Libraries that will treat computer-generated and conventionally filmed microforms in concise, nontechnical essays for the continuing education of all librarians.

Microforms for Preservation

The Council's early efforts in applying microform technology to libraries centered on the development of prototype equipment designed to make microforms easier to use, less costly to produce, and more adaptable to library processes. Although the need for more extensive resources than were available to the Council and the growing interest of commercial vendors combined to lessen attention to this activity as a Council priority, a further effort was made in 1973. The need for an automatic camera designed especially to

film catalog cards was heightened during the late sixties and seventies when many academic libraries began to microfilm their card catalogs as a hedge against natural disaster and vandalism. CLR therefore entered into a contract with Mega System Design of Toronto, Canada, to develop a prototype camera, which has subsequently been tested in several libraries. Mega has since built improved cameras of this type, based on what was learned from testing the prototype.

Other projects designed to preserve fast-deteriorating materials, such as newspapers, or to make them more readily available for scholars were also funded in the transitional years 1968-71. Council grants supported the establishment at the University of Pennsylvania of a central archive of microfilms of medieval manuscripts held in European institutions. A center for the coordination of foreign manuscript copying had been established earlier at the Library of Congress with the assistance of the Council. A 1969 study conducted by the Association of Research Libraries with CLR assistance resulted in the expansion of ARL's Foreign Newspaper Microfilming Project to include the establishment in 1973 of a Foreign Newspaper Microfilming Office at the Library of Congress. A small grant to the Dartmouth College Library in 1971 allowed that institution to make available to other libraries microfilm editions of its holdings of such rare materials as presidential election campaign documents for the years 1968-1900, the papers of Augustus Saint-Gaudens, and other collections for the specialist.

The Potential of COM

By 1970, rising costs of paper and book production helped to stimulate interest in a development that combined the best features of both microform and computer technology -- speed in the case of the computer, low-cost production and size in the case of microforms. This development was computer output microfilm (COM).

Computerized bibliographic data bases can be used for many purposes. They are useful not only for searching and retrieving discrete items of information quickly, but also for producing lengthy bibliographies, book catalogs, and other research tools and management information documents at high rates of speed. Today's computers are capable of prodigious output, often reaching one million or more characters a second. A basic problem has been to capture that output in a human-readable form, in order to take full advantage of the computer's production capability.

In the 1950s and early 1960s, the solution to that problem was generally to attach to the computer a high-speed printer, capable of printing an entire line at once. These "line printers" could produce copy at what seemed an astonishing rate of speed; however, since that rate rarely exceeds 3,000 characters a second, line-printers are entirely inadequate for dealing with computer output generated at a rate of over 30 times faster. Although line printers are still, and will continue to be, the principal output device used, a higher speed printout is desirable for many projects.

The first breakthrough in providing higher speed printout occurred in 1956, when the first computer output microfilmer appeared. This

device, which converted the computer's electronic signals to characters on microfilm, was the first example of what we now call a COM (Computer Output Microfilm) recorder.

Despite this early start, it was not until the 1970s that significant growth in COM began to occur, both in sales of COM recorders and in experimentation with new applications. The Council's interest in COM's potential dates from the CLR-supported Index Medicus project at the National Library of Medicine in the early 1960s, where new phototypesetting techniques were a precursor of later COM activity. The first Council grant made specifically for a COM project was awarded in 1970 to the Tulane University Library. Its investigators proposed to utilize COM in the production of a short-title catalog and to test its acceptance by librarians and library users. A sizable number of libraries, in addition to Tulane's, have converted or are converting their catalogs from card and book format to a COM format. COM is also being used to turn out such products as union lists of holdings, authority files, patron files, and on-order lists.

COM reader devices receive information either from magnetic tape or directly from computers and recreate it on the television-like screen of a cathode ray tube computer terminal, from which it is automatically recorded on microfilm. New COM recorders can eliminate the display step by imprinting from 10,000 to 50,000 lines of a text a minute directly on film. Depending on the reduction ratio used, a single reel of microfilm can contain the bibliographic data representing the records held in a sizable library's entire card catalog (e.g., 250,000 items)

with space left over. Moreover, this reel can be duplicated as necessary with no significant loss of quality. In most instances, COM catalogs cost less than book catalogs, no matter how the latter are produced. What is more, because of the low cost, the information contained can be easily updated and the catalog reissued. Thus, savings in both space and cost combine with availability of current information to enhance the potential of this new medium.

The Council followed these developments carefully and early in 1976 began thorough investigation into the potential of computer output microfilm for library application. As a first step, CLR brought together in January 1976 a panel of micrographics and computer experts to establish the specifics of an inquiry into the degree to which COM hardware, software, and services can be effectively applied to library services and operations.

In the first meeting, the advisory panel developed a series of questions, chiefly concerned with bibliographic applications of COM, to be answered by the principal investigator during the course of the project. His report will cover such matters as the present and prospective cost ranges for generating COM output of bibliographic data, the availability of various character fonts and page formats, the suitability of the readers and reader/printers currently available, limitations of COM formatting, reactions of users to the medium, and the identification of existing bibliographic products that are good candidates for conversion to COM. By the end of June, most of the necessary field work had been completed and an initial draft of the report was in preparation.

The Library of Congress joined the ranks of COM publishers during the year covered by this report. As an experiment, in late 1975 LC produced a microform version of the eighth edition of the Library of Congress Subject Headings, using both COM and other techniques that simulated it. This field trial had successful results. Not only did the microform version appear months ahead of the printed version, but subscribers were receptive to the format and a number were enthusiastic about it. After evaluating the experiment, the Library decided to publish a COM version of its Register of Additional Locations (RAL) in 1976. The Register has been published in printed form since 1965 as a supplement to the National Union Catalog and contains additional locations for titles published from the year 1956 to the present. New locations reported to the RAL through 1975 have been entered into a machine-readable file that now contains approximately 1.75 million titles with an average of 12.4 locations per title. Since the Register can quickly give a library the names of other institutions owning a desired book, it is widely used to facilitate interlibrary loan.

A CLR grant was made recently to enable the Library of Congress to conduct two studies related to the Register of Additional Locations. The first study will identify machine-readable data bases from which location reports can be obtained, thus allowing for a rapid expansion of the RAL data base. A survey of libraries having machine-readable data bases will be conducted, followed by on-site interviews with those whose data bases seem to be likely prospects from which to draw

location information. Should the Library be able to capitalize on existing data bases, the resulting enlarged RAL file might be an important element in the development of a national interlibrary loan network.

The second study will be carried out concurrently with the publication of the Register in microform. Purchasers of the Register in the new format will be asked to participate in an LC survey. Their responses will, among other things, assist the Library in determining the most desirable frequency of publication of the microform Register and whether, in fact, this edition could supplant the printed version.

Microforms - Other Aspects

Two other projects focusing on problems associated with microforms came to an end in the past year. The first involved the feasibility of extending to a university campus a centralized information dissemination service that uses microforms.

In 1973, the Governors State University Library received a CLR grant for an experiment to test the feasibility of using the Selected Research in Microfiche (SRIM) Service of the National Technical Information Service (NTIS) on a university-wide basis. NTIS is an official depository for all scientific and technical reports forwarded to it by federal agencies and their contractors and grantees. It is responsible for the retention of the material and for the bibliographic control, duplication, and dissemination of such documents. Through its SRIM Service NTIS automatically supplies to users microfiche copies of newly accessioned documents in subject categories chosen by the subscriber at a considerably

lower price than that of copies furnished in response to specific orders. The Governors State Library proposed to effect further reductions in cost by acting as a sort of broker between NTIS and the university faculty. Under the grant, the library prepared subject interest profiles of individual faculty members and combined the categories into a single order. NTIS furnished the documents on microfiche and the library reproduced the microfiche in the necessary quantities, distributing them to the participating faculty members and keeping the master copy for its own collections.

The experiment was scheduled to last nine months, after which an evaluation would be made. Following an initial three-month trial, organization problems within NTIS delayed further work on the project until the first six months of 1975 when the program was resumed with refined profiles and procedures. During the course of the project, the Library acquired a total of 12,705 NTIS documents, which, when combined with the number reproduced, reduced the cost of individual items to 34.5¢ per document (the regular SRIM rate is 45¢ per document). Following its evaluation, the library concluded that the redistribution service was feasible in terms of cost and practical in terms of procedure. It also provided side benefits for the library by enhancing its collection and enlarging its ability to serve faculty members. The library's final report noted, however, that the service is totally dependent on the stability and service provided by the main distributor, in this case NTIS. Without this stability at NTIS, a program of the kind attempted at Governors State cannot function efficiently on a long-term basis.

The second microform project completed this year addressed the need of librarians, many of whom lack technical knowledge, to evaluate the various types and brands of microform equipment marketed for library use.

In late 1975, the Council published Evaluating Microfiche Readers: A Handbook for Librarians. The 64-page book, written by William R. Hawken with the assistance of the ALA's Library Technology Project and the Council's micrographics specialist, was the result of a CLR-initiated project to find a means of helping librarians determine inexpensively and reliably the most suitable microfiche reader for their purposes. The handbook contains four test microfiche that allow a nontechnically trained person to evaluate microfiche readers and reader-printers intended for use in libraries. Reviews of the work describe it as "a model of technical writing," "concise," "a positive step," and "a most useful aid." Copies were sent by the American Library Association to subscribers to the Library Technology Reports and by the Association of Research Libraries to its members. In addition to providing copies for review, CLR distributed the balance of the 2612-copy edition to requesting libraries. The supply of free copies has been exhausted. However, the Council has kept a record of institutions that received a copy and will supply requesting libraries with names of nearby institutions from which they may borrow the handbook.

Producing materials in a microform format and organizing them into a coherent collection would be useless endeavors without the existence of an apparatus that allows a potential user to locate the desired document. For reasons of economics, micropublication of

uncopyrighted and out-of-print works no longer covered by copyright is normally in the form of large sets, containing hundreds or thousands of items. Bibliographic aids provided with the sets are frequently scanty and the production or acquisition of catalog cards for individual items is too expensive to consider. The Council has recently awarded a small grant to Suzanne Dodson, head of the Government Publications and Microforms Division of the University of British Columbia Library, to enable her to complete a book designed to facilitate the use of these large collections. The guide will contain descriptions of approximately 200 sets of wide general interest. The entries will incorporate details of the contents of each collection, along with references to published reviews. The work will be helpful not only to libraries that own the sets but also to all libraries with facilities for reading microforms, for they may use the guide to determine if materials desired by their patrons appear in the collections described by Mrs. Dodson and therefore available on interlibrary loan.

Although Council allocations for preservation activities have lessened in recent years, its attention to programs in micrographics has increased. In fiscal 1976, grants of \$102,313 were awarded and \$20,000 was set aside for an ongoing Council-administered project.

LIBRARY MANAGEMENT

The study of management as a discrete discipline is a product of the twentieth century, resulting largely from the performance of industry (especially American industry) during World War II. The focus of management studies to the present day has been on business and industry, for there the results of management decisions can be easily measured. Since the turn of the century, however, the growth of public service institutions has been phenomenal, to the point where management expert Peter Drucker estimates that from 50 to 60 percent of the gross national product goes not to the business sector, but to or through public-service institutions. "The nonbusiness, public-service institutions do not need management less than business," he wrote recently. "They may need it more....Managing the service institution is likely to be the frontier of management for the rest of this century."

The responsibilities involved in managing a library are no less complex than those involved in managing a business of similar size. Unique to the library are the intellectually challenging fields of bibliography, the classification of knowledge, its storage, and provision for its use. But most academic and public librarians are book- or information-oriented; their backgrounds are generally in the academic disciplines and, until recently, most have had little or no special training for management.

The need to adapt for library use sound management techniques developed in government, business, academic administration, and elsewhere is made even more critical by the phenomenal growth experienced by libraries in this century. This growth may be illustrated by statistics

published in 1975-76 by the Association of Research Libraries. The hundred ARL members reported that together they held over 217 million volumes in their collections; at the same time, their combined operating budgets had swelled to over \$522 million. In contrast, a hundred years ago the total income of all colleges and universities, in which their libraries shared, was approximately \$4.5 million, and a university library could be designated as a "major academic library" if it had at least 5000 volumes.

The Council has always had as one of its major goals the improvement of library administration. In the early years, CLR-supported management projects focused on specific aspects of administration: planning for buildings and for space utilization, studying manpower shortages, developing personnel practices and policies, analyzing the relation of the library to the bookseller, and dealing with fire insurance and legal requirements. In 1968, the Council initiated discussions with librarians, educators, and university administrators that resulted in a more coherent, coordinated program designed to improve academic library management practices.

Management of University Libraries

The first grant in this area went in 1969 to the Association of Research Libraries for a preliminary study by Booz, Allen & Hamilton of management practices in large university libraries. The study team was assisted by an advisory committee of leading academic librarians and university presidents, who supplied the insights, guidance, and specialized knowledge that were needed as the investigators moved into what was, for them, largely unexplored territory. The resulting publication, Problems in University Library Management, has been the point of departure for much subsequent activity. One important outgrowth was the establishment

within ARL of the CLR-funded Office of University Library Management Studies (OMS), now in its sixth year of operation.

Since the Booz, Allen & Hamilton study dealt with general management applications for all large university libraries, it was felt that a logical second step would be to apply those principles to the operations of a specific institution. Accordingly, in 1971 the Council contracted again with Booz, Allen & Hamilton, which by now had a fair amount of useful experience in the area, to conduct a study of the organization and staffing of the Columbia University Libraries. The newly appointed director of ARL's Office of University Library Management Studies worked as a member of the Booz, Allen team, gaining invaluable on-the-job training for his challenging assignment.

Office of University Library Management Studies

Since August 1970, when OMS was established, the Council has made grants of more than \$550,000 toward its work. In the six years since, an increasing amount of support each year has come from ARL and from the sale of the office's products and services.

OMS activities are grouped around management research, information collection and dissemination, and organizational training. In the area of research, the office's most significant contribution has been the design and application of the Management Review and Analysis Program (MRAP), a highly structured procedure for university library use in conducting an internal assessment of management practices, goals, and objectives. To carry out its self-study, each library appoints a team that uses MRAP procedures to examine the decision-making process and to recommend organizational changes that are needed to improve day-to-day library operations. Johns Hopkins University began its self-analysis in September 1975, bringing to 22 the number of institutions that have

participated in MRAP. During the past year, OMS staff assisted with this and other studies and received final MRAP reports from Indiana University, the University of Kentucky, the University of Toronto, Pennsylvania State University, and the University of Utah.

The office's main effort in the exchange of information is through its Systems and Procedures Exchange Center (SPEC), which collects data and documentation related to academic and research library management and makes the material available to the library community. The information is issued primarily through SPEC Flyers, two-page brief analyses of the data collected, and SPEC Kits, which contain a variety of related documents. Of the nine flyers and kits issued during 1975-76, four include information gleaned from a major survey of user services conducted by SPEC in November 1975. The topics covered are user surveys, user statistics and studies, physical access in ARL libraries, and bibliographic access in ARL libraries. Information compiled from OMS' research activities is also disseminated through the ARL Management Supplements and Occasional Papers as well as articles in library journals.

To promote organizational training and development, the OMS staff carried out several programs during the 1975-76 year. The first Library Management Skills Institute, held in Philadelphia in July 1975, was well received; three more are scheduled for the balance of 1976. The office also added several titles to its collection of training films. These are loaned with accompanying discussion materials to requesting libraries. A further endeavor involves the design of topical training modules, which, when testing is completed, will be made available to libraries at a modest cost. The first of these, on performance appraisal,

is being tested in a pilot program at McGill University. Developed jointly by OMS staff and library personnel, the pilot project has been operating for approximately six months.

A project to evaluate the impact of the OMS Management Review and Analysis Program will be undertaken by two Pennsylvania State University faculty members: Edward R. Johnson, associate librarian and assistant dean of libraries, and Stuart H. Mann, associate professor of operations research. The goal of the 12-month Council-funded study is to determine whether behavioral, attitudinal, or organizational changes have occurred in the climate, overall performance, and effectiveness of libraries that have gone through the MRAP process. Information will be collected by means of a survey that combines questionnaires and personal interviews. The project directors hope the study will result in an evaluative tool that will be useful to the Association of Research Libraries, to MRAP participants, and to other libraries wishing to assess organizational development programs.

Management Planning and Research

The study of the Columbia University Libraries, described earlier in this section, resulted in a report that not only evaluated the existing organization and staffing of the libraries, but projected future requirements, recommended a plan of library organization, and prescribed a detailed staffing pattern. In order to implement the recommendations, Columbia established a Libraries Planning Office, funded for its first three years principally by the Council and partially by the university itself. The office is now entirely supported by the university. The Planning Office has worked continuously to plan for the effective use of all the library and information resources available to the university.

A revised edition of the Planning Office's report on the new administrative organization of the Columbia University Libraries was published in late 1975. It contains detailed organizational descriptions of the libraries housing distinctive collections, such as the Health Sciences Library, the Rare Book and Manuscript Library, the East Asian Library, and the Columbiana Library. The report represents a significant milestone in the further implementation of Columbia's reorganization plan.

The Columbia study and the subsequent work of the Planning Office have provided one model for an approach to improving library management. Council support for a related effort, the establishment of a model research and development (R&D) unit within a single library system, ended this year. The Joint University Libraries (JUL) of Nashville, Tennessee, established an R&D unit in July 1970. The unit's mission was to apply research and development techniques to library problems defined by the JUL constituent libraries (Vanderbilt University, George Peabody and Scarritt colleges) and to publish reports and studies that could be helpful to other academic libraries as well.

In the final report, the unit's director listed 32 major projects completed during the past six years. The wide-ranging activities dealt with such topics as the preparation of uniform statistical forms for use in all libraries, an affirmative action plan, development of a library service policy, the design of a government documents section as a separate entity within the library system, and planning for the implementation of JUL's participation in SOLINET. Three important projects were concluded in the past year. The first was a technical services cost study, designed to give more credibility to JUL's program budgeting mechanism, which had been developed earlier in the grant period.

Second, the R&D unit developed a planning document to provide the foundation upon which to base both short- and long-range planning for the JUL system. The third project was a study of the organizational roles of the divisional libraries in JUL's cooperative structure. This study, along with other organizational analyses, resulted in an administrative reorganization within JUL to take effect on July 1, 1976.

In addition, the unit has worked closely with the Vanderbilt Computer Center to develop a computerized access-control system. A user survey was designed and conducted in March 1976, in an attempt to mesh the library's goals and objectives with the needs of the library's patrons. In summing up their accomplishments, the Research and Development Unit's final report stated that "the work that was initiated has made an impact on the Joint University Libraries which will not end."

Management in the Smaller Institution

Management problems are not restricted to large university libraries or library systems. Small and mid-sized academic libraries face similar pressures caused by upward spiraling costs, rapid technological developments, and increased demands to be more accountable to students, faculties, and college administrations. The need for management skills that exists in university libraries can be found as well in smaller institutions that thus far frequently have lacked the means for self-improvement. In the belief that some of the experience gained through the MRAP process could be usefully applied to smaller college and university libraries, the Council initiated a new Academic Library Development Program in 1975. The program began with a grant to the University of North Carolina at Charlotte (UNCC) for a pilot project enabling the library

to engage in a broad range of self-studies, similar to MRAP but tailored to meet the needs of smaller institutions.

The first step was the recruitment of the principal investigator. Next, a team composed of UNCC library staff members began its study of the broad issues of general concern to the library. These included historical and environmental assessments, consideration of the library's internal needs, and an analysis of library goals and objectives. In the spring of 1976, the study team appointed task forces to provide detailed reports and recommendations on management structure and processes, human resource development and use, library resources and services, and future demands for technology and facilities. A major product of the pilot program, scheduled for completion in late summer of 1976, is a library self-study manual that may be used by other small to moderate-sized academic libraries. From the beginning, the UNCC project has been assisted by the director of the ARL Office of University Library Management Studies and by an advisory committee composed of college presidents, academic librarians, library school professors, and officials of higher education associations concerned with accreditation.

By the end of fiscal year 1976, it had been determined that to ensure the maximal benefit of the model program to libraries, further testing at other institutions would be required. The Council made a supplemental appropriation in May to cover the cost of testing and evaluating the Academic Library Development Program at several institutions of appropriate size and character.

Specific Management Projects

While most of the foregoing programs of the 1970s have dealt with

the improvement of management practices in a broad sense, during the last six years the Council has continued its earlier support of programs that focus on specific aspects of library administration. For example, a 1972 Council grant made it possible for the Cornell University libraries to undertake a twelve-month program of staff development, with guidance from the Center for Planning and Development of the American Management Association. A CLR-supported study entitled Economics of Academic Libraries, by William Baumol and Matityahu Marcus, was published in 1973 by the American Council on Education. In addition to an analysis of the growth trends of such variables as library salaries and wages, book expenditures, and student enrollment, the volume contains formulas and procedures to guide individual librarians in the projection of their library's future growth and in budget preparation. A study of library lighting and a survey of administrative information concerning business school libraries also received CLR support during this period.

A grant this year to Washington University in St. Louis, Missouri, provides another example of support for improving specific administrative procedures. Using the Washington University Library as the site, staff will attempt to develop a procedure to improve the internal financial auditing of university libraries. Viewing the library as a fiscal system, the plan calls first for the definition of critical fiscal control points in the library, such as cash purchases of books and library materials, collection of fines, duplicate payments, vendor credits, photocopy income, etc. Following this, an actual audit will be conducted and evaluated. An advisory group of university auditors, representatives of comparable universities, and the ARL Office of University Library Management Studies will aid in reviewing and refining

the criteria to help assure their applicability to other university libraries. After careful testing, a manual containing the auditing criteria will be prepared.

The Council's efforts in behalf of improved management functions in academic libraries of all types have grown in recent years to the point where projects such as those here described account for a significant portion of program funds. During the fiscal year \$41,509 was allocated for management programs and \$200,000 earmarked for continuation of an ongoing program. It should be remembered, also, that management improvement is an important goal of other projects, such as the Academic Library Management Intern Program, described elsewhere in this report.

LIBRARIES AND THEIR USERS

In a leading encyclopedia, libraries are defined as "collections of books and other forms of records housed, organized, and interpreted to meet broad and varying needs of people for information, knowledge, recreation, and aesthetic enjoyment." This cogent definition not only combines the connotations of the word "library" as both a collection and a place, it also recognizes the need for a collection to be "interpreted," whether through printed or computerized guides or through the direct services of a knowledgeable librarian. Further, the definition emphasizes the point that the activity surrounding the collection is undertaken for one reason: "to meet broad and varying needs of people." Much attention has been given in this discussion of Council activities to projects intended to improve the internal procedures and processes of libraries. But technologies, computers, networks, and microforms are only mechanisms, the tools that help libraries more effectively assist scholars and other users in meeting their requirements for information and knowledge.

From the beginning, the Council has devoted a substantial part of its funds to projects leading to the improvement of library services to users. Prior to 1970, the most pressing needs in this aspect of library work appeared to be in two areas: the development of cooperative acquisitions programs to enable libraries to include in their collections books and periodicals that might otherwise be unavailable to their users, and the preparation of bibliographical tools to provide scholars and other users of libraries with quick and easy access to the materials they require in their research.

Acquisitions Programs

Two important acquisitions programs have received Council support. In providing that support, the Council took care not to violate one of its earliest policies -- that CLR would not provide funds for individual libraries to meet their local requirements for buildings, collections, or staff. This decision was made in the realization that the needs of all libraries in these areas are so overwhelming that no private organization can begin to meet them. However, it is sometimes possible to initiate or support programs that will assist many libraries, and the Council attempts to do so when it can. The United States Book Exchange (USBE -- now known as the Universal Serials and Book Exchange) and the Farmington Plan were programs that met this criterion.

The USBE was founded in 1948 to serve as a center for the exchange among libraries of duplicates of books and periodicals having potential value for research but insufficient market value to make them attractive to dealers. With a stock that includes millions of items, USBE serves over a thousand institutions, American and foreign. The economics of the operation were from the beginning a source of concern. Two Council grants, in 1957 and again in 1971, enabled USBE to study its operations and procedures, to redefine its activities, and to explore possibilities and bases for future expansion and financing. In 1973, USBE reported that this help from the Council had made it possible to maintain services on a self-supporting basis.

The second program, the Farmington Plan, also started in 1948 when some 60 American libraries began to share responsibility for the acquisition of foreign publications in certain subject fields. After ten years, participants in the Farmington Plan had become acutely aware of its deficiencies and resolved to make the necessary changes. The Council supported the survey and evaluation that resulted in a changed and improved activity.

Eventually the Farmington Plan was superseded when in 1961 Congress at last appropriated funds to implement the Public Law 480 program. P.L.-480 allows U.S.-owned foreign currencies to be used for the purchase and servicing of books, periodicals, and related materials, and their distribution to American university and research libraries. CLR supported two studies of the new program by Dr. Mortimer Graves, former president of the American Council of Learned Societies. The first helped stimulate Congress to appropriate the needed funds (the plan had been authorized in 1958); the second study reviewed the program ten years later, with an emphasis on the individual user of the foreign materials. In 1969, a grant to Columbia University supported a complementary study of the program, dealing this time primarily with the impact of the program on participating libraries.

The P.L.-480 program, now known as the Special Foreign Currency Program, has been administered by the Library of Congress since its inception. At the end of fiscal year 1975, LC reported that 19,725,108 commercial, institutional, and governmental publications had been acquired to date for all participants in the program.

Guides to Resources

The Council has been equally selective among the many proposals it receives that concern the preparation of bibliographical tools intended to aid a library in its selection of materials and to help librarians and scholars locate needed resources. Again, because of the vast number of worthwhile projects in this area and the limited funds available for their support, the Council selects only those that seem to be of greatest benefit to libraries and scholars as a whole. In the early years, Council support led to the publication of union lists (e.g., Union List of Serials in Libraries in the United States and Canada,

National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections), providing the names of libraries holding certain items; bibliographies (Répertoire International des Sources Musicales, "Masters' Theses in the Pure and Applied Sciences"); and book selection tools (Law Books Recommended for Libraries).

Two specialized bibliographic tools received CLR grants during the past year. In July 1975, the American Council of Learned Societies (ACLS) received an award to support a survey of medieval Arabic manuscript collections in the United States. The survey was unanimously recommended by the ACLS Arabic Studies Group as a project of "fundamental importance to the future of Arabic scholarship." Dr. Thomas J. Martin, a research associate in New York University's Department of Near Eastern Languages and Literatures, is carrying out the survey. During the year the scope of the survey was broadened to include Persian and Turkish manuscripts as well as Arabic, since all three languages use the same script and are often housed together. Dr. Martin has corresponded with known depositories, visited major collections, and submitted drafts of reports for comment by responsible persons at each library covered in the survey. Following the receipt of approved draft entries, Dr. Martin will begin work on the final report.

The second CLR grant went to Frank Rodgers, director of libraries at Portland State University, to assist him in completing research for a "Manual of British Government Publications." There is no general guide to British government publications comparable to Boyd and Rips' United States Government Publications. Mr. Rodgers' manual is intended to become such a source and should therefore be of great use to researchers. Mr. Rodgers spent the major portion of his 1975-76 sabbatical leave in England, where he surveyed and prepared annotations for documents in several libraries, principally in the

University of Southampton and the British Library. At the year's end, he reported that most of his research was completed and he was ready to begin work on his report to the Council. Still ahead of him is the work on the manual itself.

Donald M. Jacobs, associate professor of history at Northeastern University in Boston, Massachusetts, was the recipient of an earlier CLR grant to assist him in the final preparation of an index to four pre-Civil War black newspapers, published between 1827 and 1841. Camera-ready copy of the manuscript was submitted in late 1975 to Greenwood Press for publication in 1976.

Academic Libraries and their Users

The Council's special clientele has always been academic and research libraries; in this area of activity, as in all others, particular attention has been given to their needs.

College libraries have always had limited funds for book purchase. With the cost per volume soaring (the average price per volume of hardcover books was \$16.19 in 1975), the necessity for college libraries to choose wisely is critical. The Council early recognized this need and, in cooperation with the American Library Association and academic specialists, supported the publication in 1967 of Books for College Libraries (BCL), which listed more than 53,000 basic titles. Because lists of this sort are out of date the moment they appear, a proposal was made for a periodical publication that would evaluate books on a current basis. Again through ALA, CLR provided developmental funds to establish Choice, a monthly book selection journal, which became self-supporting in 1969.

In September 1974, Choice added a column for the evaluation of recently issued periodicals. To edit the column, Choice called upon Evan Ira Farber,

librarian at Earlham College and author of the Classified List of Periodicals for the College Library. The fifth edition of the Classified List appeared in 1972, but, because of the inevitable time lag that characterizes compilations of this sort, it contained only those periodicals that had begun publication before 1969. The new column, "Periodicals for College Libraries," provides not only a continual update to the Classified List but also the material for subsequent editions. A small grant was awarded to Earlham College in 1975 to help defray expenses incurred by the library in the preparation of the column.

While Choice and BCL provide academic librarians with extremely useful tools for book selection, both demand that the libraries using them develop their own selection procedures to determine which of the listed books will be acquired. Unfortunately, many of the country's most understocked college libraries are also understaffed; often both the time and the training required to make the proper decisions are lacking. It was to address this problem that the Council developed a plan for a core collection -- the 40,000 basic titles any four-year liberal arts college must have in its library if it intends to provide students with an adequate education. After some discussion with ALA's Association of College and Research Libraries, it was determined that the core collection concept could be applied to a second edition of the 1967 Books for College Libraries. A new feature would be the use of computerized techniques to produce the catalog. Utilizing the Library of Congress' MARC format, reducing the number of titles to be included, and expanding the amount of cataloging data per title, the second edition of Books for College Libraries was designed to be more than a revision. As stated in the introduction, the project's purpose was to produce "a highly selective retrospective tool as a counterpart to the current services of Choice." In 1975, ALA

published Books for College Libraries: a Core Collection of 40,000 Titles in a six-volume paperback set.

Although one of the set's reviewers called it the "most sophisticated booklist published by ALA in forty years," the problem of obsolescence is still inevitable. Project planners faced up to that in devising the mechanism for the production of this second edition, called BCL II. The introduction states: "Through the cooperation of Choice and the corps of BCL II contributors and through the use of computer technology, the organization, the subject and bibliographic skills, and the machinery exist to maintain a continuing and useful service to the undergraduate library."

The Library in Undergraduate Education

There is no doubt that the programs just described will provide needed assistance to students and librarians. However the Council's primary interest in this area during the last six years has been focused on a much more basic aspect of library use. In the late 1960s not enough was being done to promote the library as an important facet of undergraduate learning or to find the means by which the library could provide better educational opportunities for students. The Council, therefore, began to sponsor a variety of projects that had the common goal of finding imaginative, effective ways to serve students. The establishment of the MIT Model Engineering Library, previously described, was one such project, for here advanced techniques and methods were taken out of the laboratory and put into a working library, where students could have access to them. In 1970, the Council and NEH jointly sponsored a project at the Stony Brook campus of the State University of New York, where a faculty-student team approach was used to develop units of source materials useful in the teaching of history. The project thus helped to assist in the training of young historians and history undergraduates. The next year the Council

supported a program at the University of Lancaster in England for an analysis of user response to procedural or technological changes at the Library. These changes, which had occurred in the areas of circulation, duplication of stock, and binding, had resulted from an ongoing general management research project.

These programs contributed to a growing body of new ideas on the ways libraries could serve the undergraduate user. But the Council was interested in a much broader problem: the need to help nonresearch academic libraries define for themselves an effective role in the educational process. No one questioned the need for colleges and universities to have libraries or that those libraries should play an important part in the education of students. Yet the mechanisms that allow the library to contribute actively to this educational process had proved to be so elusive, the search so frustrating, that on many campuses the library had in effect become a silent partner, a passive force in the academic environment. A new approach was needed, something that would stimulate college and university administrators, faculties, and librarians to take a new look at the library's role in the academic community. Thus the Council in 1969 initiated the College Library Program (CLP) and with the National Endowment for the Humanities established a fund (eventually reaching \$1,400,000) from which matching grants could be made to individual colleges and universities.

The program calls for librarians, administrators, faculty, and, in some cases, students in four-year undergraduate institutions to develop cooperatively projects designed to enhance the library's role in the education of students. Creative yet practical plans receive grants for five-year periods, during which the institution must commit itself to match the CLR-NEH contribution with funds not already allocated to the library. To date, 24 institutions

have participated in the College Library Program. The number includes Wabash College, which does not accept federal funds and therefore receives support from the Council alone. The libraries are located in institutions that vary widely in size, type, and geographic locale. Four of the institutions can be classified as state-supported universities with 20,000 students or more; five are small, private colleges with enrollments of under a thousand. At least half have enrollments of approximately 1,000-5,000 students. Six have predominantly black enrollments; three are for men only and one is for women only. Nineteen states are represented, stretching from coast to coast. In each of the institutions a program has been developed that appears to suit the current academic environment and to represent a significant step beyond past efforts at that institution.

In the summer of 1975, a team of evaluators visited 12 of the libraries in an attempt to determine whether the College Library Program so far had been successful. The evaluation was based on answers to a questionnaire sent to the project director prior to the visit and on interviews with librarians, students, administrators, and faculty. Each project was evaluated in terms of past activities in the institution; how much cooperation already existed; how many of the faculty, students, administrators, and librarians were ready to bridge the traditional communications gap -- in short the size of the hurdles to be overcome before measurable results could be discerned. Despite the problems encountered by the participating institutions (nearly all had to make major modifications of original purposes at the end of either the first or second year), the evaluating team found that "all had achieved some benefits and made some progress towards avowed ends."

The team discovered that, at a minimum, the joint program focused the

attention of the administration on the importance of the library in the total teaching effort of the institution. At the most, the learning process was greatly strengthened, since the program brought faculty and librarians together (for the first time on some campuses) in new ways designed to enlarge the educational perspectives of students and improve their investigative skills. The fact that more students were actively encouraged and given occasion to use the library than had previously been the case could not be overlooked. Finally, because each program had elements that could be adapted profitably to other libraries, a ripple effect was often produced, as evidenced by requests from nearby colleges desiring to develop programs of their own.

After measuring these results against their necessarily flexible yardstick, the evaluation team concluded that "the need to continue this program is in short a firm conviction." The team further concluded that new guidelines for the program would not only aid interested colleges in obtaining a clearer understanding of the program's goals, but would enable the Council and NEH to exercise more efficient procedures in reviewing proposals. The newly developed guidelines provide, among other things, for an initial review of preliminary CLP proposals by the Council. Final proposals will be sent to NEH, which administers a review panel that selects those most worthy of funding. The review panel will meet each year in the fall for programs to begin the succeeding year.

No grants were awarded during fiscal year 1976 while the evaluation was being conducted and procedures revised.

Directly related to the CLR-NEH College Library Program is Eastern Michigan University's Project LOEX (Library Orientation-Instruction Exchange), a clearinghouse for information and materials relating to academic library orientation instruction. LOEX was established in May 1972 as a result of

Eastern Michigan University's Library Outreach Orientation Program, a recipient of a CLP award, and has grown rapidly since. Over 500 academic libraries are members of the clearinghouse, with the privilege of borrowing materials on library orientation and instruction programs placed on deposit. They also receive the LOEX newsletter. Materials contributed by member libraries include workbooks, video tapes, program descriptions, surveys, and bibliographies. On an informal basis, LOEX staff provide assistance to librarians interested in conducting research in the field and participate in workshops and meetings. A most useful activity has been the construction of traveling exhibits of LOEX materials, which were used in thirteen states and Canada in 1975. In her first annual report, the LOEX project director noted that she was "gratified to witness the active participation and interest of many enthusiastic orientation instruction librarians who are sharing their expertise with our office in exchange for information and assistance ... the reason for our existence." A three-year Council grant in 1974 provides LOEX with the funds it needs until Eastern Michigan can take over its support.

In other sections of this report there have been several examples of how CLR has supported a variety of approaches to the solution of a particular library problem. In attempting to improve library services to undergraduates and to encourage libraries to assume a greater role in their education, the same multi-approach technique has been used. In late 1975 the Library Service Enhancement Program (LSEP) was initiated by the Council to stimulate activities intended to result in the more imaginative, effective involvement of the academic library in the teaching-learning process. These goals are the same as those toward which the College Library Program strives -- the difference is in the approach.

Under the Library Service Enhancement Program, library directors designate

a staff member as project librarian to explore with faculty, students, and administrators ways of integrating the library more fully into the educational process. With faculty assistance, the project librarian designs and implements creative programs that will expand the library's role in the academic life of the college or university. The Council grant pays the salary and benefits of the designated librarian, who is relieved of normal duties for the academic year in order to spend full time on the project. Library funds thus released are used to appoint for the year a beginning professional librarian and to pay for necessary travel and related project expenses.

The Council received over 600 requests for applications, and 212 college and university libraries completed the application process. In order to select the libraries to receive awards, applicants were divided into four groups so that institutions of generally similar size and characteristics would be competing. All applications were first read and rated by a seven-member review committee, which then narrowed the field further in a day of discussion. Site visits were made to a number of institutions, and the committee made the final selection in a subsequent meeting. The successful libraries, serving student populations ranging from 842 to over 20,000, are located at Cornell University, DePauw University, Earlham College, Lawrence University, Lewis and Clark College, University of New Hampshire, North Carolina Agricultural and Technical University, Oregon State University, Presbyterian College, University of South Carolina, State University College at Potsdam (N.Y.), and West Georgia College.

The enthusiastic response to the Enhancement Program demonstrated to the Council that it had again identified a problem area (and perhaps a solution) that should be further explored. Indeed, several unsuccessful applicants wrote that developing their proposals had so stimulated their thinking that they were going ahead with at least part of their plans without outside help.

CLR has therefore decided to continue the program for the 1977-78 academic year.

The Public Library

Public as well as academic libraries play an important part in education, in addition to the recreational opportunities they afford. A Gallup poll released in January 1976 reported that 49 percent of the adults surveyed reported using a library in the last two years; in three-fourths of the cases, the one most frequently used was a public library. These libraries have been equally beset by physical and fiscal problems and have had to face as well broad social, educational, and political questions in an era of changing values.

In 1971, the Council and the National Endowment for the Humanities provided funds for a critical study by the Public Library Association (PLA) of the goals of public library service. A Strategy for Public Library Change, the resulting report, described the current role of the public library and analyzed the societal forces that are creating pressure for it to change.

It read:

In the late '60s, the vision of ever more and better libraries began to fade. Although the population was increasing, use began to decline in terms of book circulation. Today, financial support, never too secure, is diminishing at the same time that costs of operation continue to rise. Societal changes shaking all established institutions to their foundations also threaten to engulf the public library. Its most enthusiastic supporters are hard pressed in the face of harsh, cold scrutiny of rebellious taxpayers. The public library is further endangered by the emergence of new services, agencies, and institutions -- apparent competitors threatening to replace it.

"Responsibility for leadership in coordinating library services at the local level" was placed squarely on the shoulders of the public library. The

report went on to suggest the steps that must be taken to return public libraries to their essential community role.

Although the portion of Council funds awarded for programs directed at the particular needs of public libraries has not been large, several projects have had significant effects in helping libraries to find new ways of serving their readers. One of these involved taking the library's services beyond its walls through a home delivery service. An early trial of such a service was conducted in 1961 in Washington, Pennsylvania, with some support from the Council. Although the results of this demonstration were inconclusive, interest in the concept continued. In June 1967, the Council cosponsored a meeting on the subject during the American Library Association's annual conference in San Francisco. This was followed by a second pilot project at the San Antonio Public Library, which also received Council support. In this experiment, any resident of the county, library card carrier or not, could mail or telephone to the library requests to be filled by mail. This time the results of the experiment were entirely encouraging, and the San Antonio Public Library has continued the program as part of its regular service.

Numerous books-by-mail systems now have been initiated by local, county, state, and regional libraries in both the United States and Canada. A CLR-sponsored meeting prior to the ALA annual conference in 1973 enabled over 200 interested librarians to discuss ongoing programs, evaluate activities, and exchange information concerning books-by-mail. Funds for books-by-mail programs are available under Title I of the Library Services and Construction Act (LSCA). In a discussion of LSCA developments during fiscal 1975, a U.S. Office of Education spokesman wrote, "The growth of Books by Mail programs continues nationally, influenced by the increasing operational costs

of bookmobile service, as well as by the success of such programs in reaching unserved persons."

In preparing a handbook on books-by-mail programs, a doctoral candidate at Indiana State University estimated that 60 percent of the users of the service are nonlibrary users in the traditional sense. Particularly in the rural areas, books-by-mail forms the only link between many potential library users and library services. These programs succeed because of the way they evolved -- a unique library service was developed to meet the needs of a particular type of potential library user, rather than trying to adapt a user to an existing library service. Studying user characteristics and needs as a prelude to the development of new library services was recognized as a basic step in the PLA strategy study, for it was the first subject suggested as a target for extensive research.

From 1970 to 1972 users and nonusers in New York's Bedford-Stuyvesant area, whose population is 70 percent black and 11 percent Puerto Rican, were the subject of a study undertaken by Hardy R. Franklin, at that time a staff member of the Brooklyn Public Library. The project was jointly funded by the Council and NEH. With the Educational Facilities Laboratories, CLR sponsored another study, this one directed toward an analysis of use patterns in four branches of the Los Angeles Library System. Sociopsychological measurements of community attitudes and values led to recommendations of new services that might better meet community needs, forming the basis of a report entitled "A Community Responsive Branch Program: A Study of Community Attitudes for the Los Angeles Library System."

Information services available to New York State government employees have been surveyed as part of a Council-supported study conducted by the New

York State Library. With the assistance of two outside library consultants, the Library has been developing a coordinated plan for providing information services to the executive, legislative, and judiciary branches of the New York State government. A final report on the project is expected in late 1976.

When the executive board of the Public Library Association received the recommendations contained in A Strategy for Public Library Change, it immediately took steps to carry out the four-part plan of action. The first part called for a publication to be commissioned "which will be an eloquent statement to direct widespread attention to the American public library as an active community agent capable of meeting the real needs of real people today and in the future. This should be presented in layman's language, designed to capture the attention and concerns of librarians and government bodies of all types of libraries." A strategy group was appointed to develop a plan for such a publication. In their view, what was needed was a "Consumers' Handbook for Public Libraries," a guide to public library services offered to specific groups, such as children, youth, women, students, businessmen, homeowners, blacks, Spanish-speaking, etc.

In July 1974, a small Council grant to PLA enabled the group to commission prominent individuals (e.g., Saturday Review editor Norman Cousins, U.S. Senator Jacob Javits, novelist Sol Yurick) to prepare chapters for the handbook, each of which will be followed by a response from an equally prominent librarian. During the past year, several of the 36 chapters have been placed with major periodicals for publication during 1976. The American Library Association will bring the chapters together again when it publishes the consumers' handbook in 1977 as an inexpensive paperback.

One of the strongest forces affecting the development of public libraries is changing methods of education. In the past decade the concept of life-time learning for adults, involving new patterns of nontraditional study, has had the greatest impact on public libraries. In A Strategy for Public Library Change, "the move to non-campus programs" was identified as "the greatest change in post-high school education." External degree programs in England and the College Level Examination Program (CLEP) in the United States, along with scattered university programs granting credit for home study, were identified as the "vanguard of the movement." "To provide adult and continuing education" and "to support education -- formal and informal" were two of the six goals commonly agreed upon by all public librarians participating in the strategy study. Determining the best way public libraries can meet the demands of nontraditional education has indeed been a major challenge of the 1970s.

The Council was instrumental in stimulating the involvement of libraries in the early planning stages of nontraditional educational activity. In the late 1960s, when widespread interest in the subject surfaced, CLR acted to bring together the nontraditional planners and the public library leaders. Then, with the College Entrance Examination Board (CEEB) and NEH, from 1971 to 1973 the Council supported an experimental program at the Dallas Public Library to determine the role the American public library might play in external degree work. In their evaluative account of this project, entitled The Public Library in Non-Traditional Education, Jean Brooks and David Reich explain, "The concept of the Dallas Public Library Independent Study Project was that the library, functioning as a viable learning resource center, could be an active agent in orienting the unaffiliated adult student to the process of

learning, helping him to recognize how his jig-saw pieces of experiential, often short-termed and seemingly unrelated learning episodes fitted into an organized whole."

Working closely with Southern Methodist University and other neighboring institutions of higher education, the Dallas Public Library offered individuals who were unable or unwilling to attend regular class sessions an opportunity to receive academic credit on the basis of independent study and CLEP examination scores. The two-year project pointed up the necessity for libraries and educational institutions to work out new methods for cooperating with each other and with adults interested in working independently for credit. It also became clear that if libraries were adequately to serve this emerging educational need, steps would have to be taken to provide staff with training in academic counseling and guidance, to develop specialized materials, and to establish a central coordinating body to serve as a source of communication and information.

Thus in 1972 the Council joined with the College Entrance Examination Board to plan and establish, at CEEB, the Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects. Its purpose was to provide the materials, training, and other planning resources public libraries need to become effective community learning centers. The office has received support from CLR, the National Endowment for the Humanities, the U.S. Office of Education, and CEEB itself.

During its first three years, the office embarked on a series of efforts described in detail in part I of their final report. These include:

- identifying and describing services for adult independent learners.
- encouraging public libraries in different areas of the country to

participate in the planning and testing of services to independent learners in their respective communities.

- providing participating libraries with training in both service planning and service provision.
- assisting participating libraries in the testing and evaluation of planned services.

During the office's third year, public libraries in Atlanta, Baltimore, Denver, Miami, Portland (Maine), Salt Lake City, St. Louis, Tulsa, and Woodbridge (New Jersey) began to experiment with the Learner's Advisory Service, defined as a flexible program of learning opportunities for adults interested in working independently. The service adapts itself to a variety of adult interests: learning a skill, acquiring knowledge in an academic area, studying for educational credit through CLEP or the GED (high-school equivalency) certificate, or learning for leisure activities. The librarian as a learner's advisor differs from the more traditional reader's advisor in the requirements for a stronger commitment to the educational role of the public library, for in-depth skills in educational counseling, and for a wide knowledge of educational sources both inside and outside the library, beyond the provision of printed library materials.

In November 1975, a new Council grant to the Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects provided for an expansion of the Learner's Advisory Service to other small and medium-sized public libraries through a structured program of information dissemination. NEH and CEEB also assisted in this effort. The key to the program is a series of 25 seminars that were held from April to June 1976 in various sections of the country. Conducted by resource faculty teams composed of librarians and administrators from the original nine libraries, the seminars were "designed to provide a balanced

and realistic exposure to the possible benefits, pitfalls, and ramifications of implementing a Learner's Advisory Service."

Grant support for the Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects came to an end on June 30, 1976. To carry on the task of coordinating and directing the continued development of their institutions as community learning centers, the nine project libraries have formed a Consortium for Public Library Innovation, with the Minneapolis Public Library joining as the tenth member. The consortium plans to develop its own goals and structure, but an important part of its endeavors will be the continued support of the Learner's Advisory Service.

The Council will continue to search for ways of improving library services to users and of reaching those who have not yet benefited from library programs and activities. During fiscal 1976, awards of \$239,243 were made in this significant area. An additional \$210,000 has been designated for continuation of the Library Service Enhancement Program.

VI

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

While most of the other areas of Council interest can be traced to programs initiated in its early years, it was not until the late 1960s that the Council was able to turn its attention to another serious matter: the need to attract additional highly qualified individuals to the library profession, and, once there, to retain them. Librarianship can count among its members many persons with needed talents and competencies, high levels of intellect and insight, and dedication to service. But for many years there appeared to be an insufficient number of first-rate people available to assume the leadership of the nation's academic and research libraries. Another aspect of the problem -- perhaps it is contributory -- is the lack of opportunities for librarians to increase their skills and enrich their professional experience. Such opportunities have been available to their faculty colleagues for many years. In 1969, the Council introduced the first of several programs whose primary focus is to provide librarians with opportunities for professional development and thus augment a growing reservoir of top-level talent upon which the library profession may draw to undertake the challenges of library service in the years to come.

Fellowship Program

Over 180 outstanding midcareer librarians have been designated as CLR Fellows since the Fellowship Program was initiated in 1969. Each Fellow spends a minimum of three months pursuing a self-developed study project aimed at improving his or her competence in the substantive, administrative, or technical aspects of librarianship. Over the years,

many of the recipients have published books and articles based at least in part on their experiences and have reported to their colleagues at conferences, seminars, and workshops. According to some knowledgeable observers, the CLR Fellowship Program has been largely responsible for much of the increased positive activity and thinking that have been taking place within the profession during the past few years.

This past year, 16 librarians received fellowships for the 18-month period that will end in September 1977. Among the Fellows, who must be either U. S. or Canadian citizens (or have permanent resident status in either country), is an American currently working in Paris.

This year's recipients of fellowship awards and their diverse programs are:

Mae Benne, professor, School of Librarianship, University of Washington. To identify the current functions and changes of central children's rooms in 31 metropolitan libraries and to analyze the effect of changes on organization and services.

Elizabeth Beyerly, chief, Reference, and Loan, UNESCO Library, Paris. To study the current theoretical foundations of the United Nations and UNESCO depository system and to determine the status of this system in selected African libraries.

Susan D. Csaky, head, Department of Government Publications, University of Kentucky Libraries. To study the organizational structure and publishing policies of the European Community for the purpose of developing a functional classification system for European Community documents.

Shirley A. Edsall, assistant professor, School of Information and Library Studies, State University of New York at Buffalo. To study the administration, utilization, and collection development policies of government document collections in community college libraries that have been designated as depositories.

Richard D. Hershcopf, assistant director for public services, Colorado State University Libraries. To make a comparative and historical study of the subject-divisional arrangement of collections.

Paul Jonan Ho, catalog librarian, East Asian Library, University of Pittsburgh. To investigate Japan's library resources on the People's Republic of China and to study ways of facilitating their use through international library cooperation.

Orlyn B. LaBrake, assistant director of libraries, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute (N.Y.). For a short-term program to enhance her management skills.

Isaac T. Littleton, director of libraries, North Carolina State University. To study the role of state commissions or boards of higher education in the development of libraries.

William M. McClellan, music librarian, University of Illinois at Urbana. To develop guidelines for the use of institutions of higher education in evaluating their music collections and services.

Robert L. Mowery, humanities librarian, Illinois Wesleyan University. To study continuous revision policies of the Library of Congress classification system.

Katherine Ann Peters, head librarian, Kauai Community College (Hawaii).

To examine learning resources and tutorial services in study centers of the British Open University and determine their possible application to the situation in Hawaii.

Elsbeth Pope, associate professor, College of Librarianship, University of South Carolina. To study bibliographic control and use of bibliographic data for books published in England, partially through an internship at the British National Bibliography.

Catherine J. Reynolds, head, Government Documents Division, University of Colorado Libraries. To study space planning for government document collections in research libraries.

Katherine M. Rottsoik, reference librarian, St. Olaf College (Minn.).

To examine orientation and instruction programs at several colleges for the purpose of designing a comprehensive program for students at St. Olaf College.

Anita R. Schiller, reference librarian/bibliographer, University of California, San Diego. To examine the interface of the commercial sector and the academic library in the provision of social science data base services, to determine the library's impact on these services, and to analyze emerging policy implications.

Philip Schwarz, automation development librarian, University of Wisconsin, Stout. To examine the role of locally generated title derivative indexing in academic and public libraries.

Academic Library Management Intern Program

Initiated in 1973, the Academic Library Management Intern Program is designed to assist in the development of managers for the nation's large research and academic libraries. This fall the third group of five management-minded librarians will embark on the internship experience; each will spend a full year working closely with the director and top administrative staff of one of five large academic libraries, selected for their recognized administrative excellence. During their year, the interns will have a unique opportunity to observe the techniques used by top management for dealing with day-to-day problems and to share in finding solutions in these problems. Although individual programs vary, interns may also participate in special projects that are helpful in their host institution and at the same time increase their management skills.

The Council pays the salary and benefits (up to a total of \$20,000) of each intern, based on the amount received the year prior to the internship. For this year's program, the Council responded to over 250 requests for applications, with 30 candidates completing the application procedure. Brief biographies of the five who were chosen to begin their internships in the fall of 1976 follow.

Stanton F. Biddle, Howard University, has been assigned to work with Richard M. Dougherty, library director at the University of California, Berkeley. Mr. Biddle received a B.A. in government from Howard University in 1965. Since then, his educational achievements have included an

M.L.S. from Atlanta University (1966), a Certificate in Modern Archives Administration from the American University (1969), an M.P.A. from the New York University Graduate School of Public Administration (1973), and a certificate in the Library Administrator Development Program at the University of Maryland (1974). Prior to his professional association with Howard University, Mr. Biddle held various positions with the Schomburg Center for Research in Black Culture at the New York Public Library, most recently as project director of a \$200,000 grant to the center from the National Endowment for the Humanities. He has been associate director at the Howard University Library since 1973.

William Joseph Crowe, Jr., Indiana University, will spend his year with Frederick H. Wagman, director of the University of Michigan Library. Currently enrolled in Indiana University's Ph.D. program in library science, Mr. Crowe holds a B.A. in European history and French language from Boston State College (1968) and an M.L.S. from Rutgers (1969). He began his career at the Boston Public Library, where he held positions in cataloging and acquisitions. In 1971, he moved to Indiana University, first as order librarian, then as coordinator of processing for the six regional campus libraries, a position he now holds.

Peter C. Haskell, Colgate University, will work with W. Carl Jackson, dean of the Indiana University Libraries. After receiving his B.A. from Bowdoin College in 1961, Mr. Haskell spent four years as an intelligence officer with the U. S. Army in Germany. After Rutgers awarded him an M.L.S. in 1969, he worked as a cataloger-reference librarian and assistant circulation librarian at Cornell University. In 1973 he assumed his present position as associate university librarian at Colgate.

Wilson Luquire, Indiana University, will intern with Frank P. Grisham, director of the Joint University Libraries in Nashville. Mr. Luquire completed bachelor's (Furman University, 1963) and master's (Indiana University, 1968) degrees in music before turning to the library field. He received his M.L.S. from Indiana University in 1970, has completed course work for a Ph.D. in music, and has been awarded a Ph.D. in library science at the same institution. His dissertation topic was "Selected Factors Affecting Library Staff Perceptions of an Innovative System: A Study of ARL Libraries in OCLC." Since 1969, Mr. Luquire has worked at the Indiana University Libraries as associate librarian and senior cataloger. His duties included service on the library's Management Review and Analysis Program (MRAP) study team.

Merrily E. Taylor, University of South Florida, has been assigned to work with Rutherford D. Rogers, Yale University librarian. Ms. Taylor received her B.A. in English education (1965) and M.A. in English literature (1973) from the University of South Florida. In 1968 she was awarded an M.L.S. by Florida State University, Tallahassee. Her work experience to date has been at the University of South Florida, where she has held positions in the library's reference and circulation departments. In 1971 she undertook the supervision of both the circulation and reserve departments, where she remained until 1974. A new department for collection development was created at that time; Ms. Taylor became its first head.

Advanced Study Program for Librarians

During 1975-76 the Council initiated a new professional development program, this time addressing the need of research and academic libraries for librarians with advanced study competence to work effectively

with faculty, graduate students, and other scholars. The goal of this program is to develop a pool of highly qualified "scholar-librarians." To this end, successful candidates will spend an academic year pursuing full-time graduate course work in a scholarly discipline -- one traditionally considered to be within the liberal arts and sciences -- at a graduate school of distinction in the chosen field of study. The program is not intended to support work in professional areas, such as library science, education, law, business administration, or management, nor may the funds be used for travel or writing a dissertation. Advanced Study Scholars receive stipends up to \$15,000, based on salary and normal benefits received the year prior to the study. The Council also pays graduate school tuition and fees.

The five outstanding librarians chosen during the past year as the first Advanced Study Scholars are scheduled to begin their studies in the fall of 1976. All five have master's degrees in both library science and a subject field; four of the five are currently enrolled in programs leading to the Ph.D. The award winners have demonstrated interest and competence in a variety of scholarly disciplines within the liberal arts and sciences, ranging from Iberian history and classical studies to history of the health sciences.

Biographies of the 1976-77 Advanced Study Scholars and their plans for the academic year follow.

Ellen Hodges Brow, Latin American bibliographer, University of Kansas Libraries, will spend her year at the University of Wisconsin, Madison, pursuing studies in Iberian history. A doctoral candidate at that

institution, Ms. Brow holds master's degrees in librarianship (San Jose State University, 1966) and Ibero-American area studies (University of Wisconsin, 1969). Her work experience began in 1961 when she taught English as a foreign language in Quito, Ecuador. Since then she has held several library positions involving cataloging and acquisition of Hispanic materials, culminating in her current appointment. As part of her responsibility for collection building at the University of Kansas, Ms. Brow carried out a book-buying trip to Guatemala, Costa Rica, Columbia, and Venezuela in early 1975.

Jill R. Cogan will study British imperial history, concentrating on South and Southeast Asian history, at the School of Oriental and African Studies, University of London. She received master's degrees in library science and history from the University of California, Los Angeles, in 1966 and 1973 respectively. She is currently a doctoral candidate at the same institution. Although her most recent professional position was as associate music librarian in UCLA's Music Library, Ms. Cogan hopes to continue her career as a subject area bibliographer.

Barbara Crawford Halporn received a master's degree in library science from Indiana University in 1966 and one in classics from the same institution in 1975. Since 1969 she has been the librarian for philosophy, classics, history and philosophy of science, and psychology at the Indiana University Libraries, following experiences as both a rare-books cataloger and gifts librarian. Currently enrolled as a Ph.D. candidate in classics at Indiana, Ms. Halporn plans to continue a study of the Greek language, history of science, and the classics at Harvard University during her fellowship year.

Gloria Jean Hubbard is a reference librarian at Humboldt State University, Arcata, California. She received a B.A. in Slavic languages from UCLA in 1963 and continued as a graduate student both there and at the University of Zagreb. In 1968 she was awarded a master's degree in library science from UCLA and completed an M.A. in English at the same institute this spring. Ms. Hubbard will pursue courses in comparative literature at the University of California, Berkeley, beginning this fall. In addition to her duties as reference librarian at Humboldt State, Ms. Hubbard has been responsible for cataloging microforms and has acted as subject bibliographer for the foreign language and literature, mathematics, and linguistics departments.

Nancy Whitten Zinn has spent nearly ten years in charge of a major collection in the history of health sciences (dentistry, nursing, medicine, pharmacy), in addition to being the university archivist at the University of California, San Francisco. She was granted an M.A. in history by Bryn Mawr College (1959) and an M.S. in library science by Drexel University (1962). The next year she completed an internship in medical librarianship at Emory University. Ms. Zinn plans to undertake a course of studies in the Department of History of the Health Sciences at her home institution, with related courses on the Berkeley campus. Before moving to San Francisco, she worked as head of reference and circulation at the library of the College of Physicians in Philadelphia.

The selection process for each professional development program is rigorous. Applications are reviewed by both screening and selection committees composed of eminent librarians and scholars who have knowledge particularly suited to the demands of each program. For the

Management Intern and Advanced Study Programs, interviews with leading candidates are also part of the final selection process.

University of Chicago Library Program

In its attempt to broaden the reservoir of talent available to libraries, in 1974 the Council took an experimental step when it funded a program at the University of Chicago Graduate Library School for current holders of the Ph.D. in fields other than librarianship. The program was based on the realization that talented scholars from many disciplines had found rewarding careers as librarians. Furthermore, as in the Advanced Study Program, it was felt that the library profession needs to draw on the special competencies afforded by persons with proven intellectual skills and a dedication to service, and that the entrance to the field of persons with such backgrounds might have a positive effect on the attitudes and standards of the profession.

Six candidates completed their studies and received the M.A. in librarianship under the program in August 1975, and two more began during the past year. Lack of mobility has hampered the placement of two of the original six, and one was offered and accepted a tenured teaching position. The other three, however, are working in information-related fields. One teaches in a Department of Computer Science, the second is an archivist and special collections librarian, and the third has taken a position as a reference librarian in a university library. The Chicago program will draw to a close in 1977, at which time a final assessment will be made.

Finally, although the primary goal of the Library Service Enhancement Program, described in the preceding chapter, is to improve services,

it also incorporates a professional development aspect. It is expected that the year's experience gained by the designated project librarians will augment their professional growth and strengthen their administrative skills.

The Council continues to seek ways in which it can help librarians enlarge the professional skills that will enhance library services in whatever form they may take. The volume of response from librarians to the present programs of this kind reinforces our conviction that these are important activities -- to librarians and those they serve. Professional development programs accounted for \$62,903 in new grants and fellowships this fiscal year. The grants made under the Management Intern and Advanced Study programs had been authorized during the preceding year and are therefore not included in this total. The board this year also appropriated \$320,000 for continuation of the Council's three major programs in this area.

INTERNATIONAL LIBRARY COOPERATION

"International library cooperation is assuming much greater importance to librarians in all parts of the world and is likely to be a major concern in the next quarter of a century." With these words, Norman Horrocks, director of the School of Library Service, Dalhousie University, Canada, opened a discussion of the role of the United States in world librarianship, which appeared in Library Journal's hundredth issue devoted to "Libraries in America's Future." Dr. Horrocks went on to describe the shifting focus of international cooperation: "While in the past we have thought of such things as international agreements for interlibrary loans, cooperative agreements between nations in the provision of abstracting services, the services of visiting consultants, pilot projects for public library service or assistance with the development of library schools, the future will be more technically sophisticated with the sharing of computer software and the use of advanced communications networks linked with computerized retrieval systems."

What has been expressed in this statement is the logical corollary of the earlier projection of a national library system composed of a federation of compatible networks -- that is, an international library system comprising national and multinational networks and using a variety of computerized and manual techniques to exchange bibliographic information about the world's publications. The requirements for careful planning and acceptable standards in the growth of a national system apply equally to an evolving international library system. It is only in recent years that the development of such a system has seemed remotely possible.

Early CLR Activities

The Council's interest in international activities dates from its first year of operation when, in June 1957, a CLR grant allowed the American Library Association to send a representative to an important cataloging conference in Lübeck, Germany. Programs to promote international agreements in cataloging practice have continued to take up a substantial portion of Council time and funds, for these agreements provide great benefit to libraries all over the world. Previous chapters have related such efforts as the acceptance of the International Standard Serial Number and the revision of the Anglo-American Cataloging Rules. But these represent only parts of the whole. It is through the work of the International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) that the major breakthroughs in reaching agreements have occurred.

The International Federation of Library Associations had already been working toward the coordination of cataloging practices when the Council in 1958 provided that organization with funds to plan the 1961 Paris International Conference on Cataloging Principles, which was also supported by the Council. With more than 200 participants and observers, the Paris Conference resulted in substantial agreements among nations in an area where accord had previously seemed almost impossible. A further grant in 1969 enabled the IFLA Committee on Uniform Cataloging Rules to organize a meeting of specialists in Copenhagen to review developments since the 1961 conference and to examine prospects for further advances through standardization and mechanization. Significant progress was made at this meeting toward agreement on standards of bibliographical description for catalog entries.

In its first 15 years, the Council also supported the work of other international organizations interested in making library and archival materials more accessible on a world-wide basis. Some of the grants assisted the development of particular publications. For example, a series of awards went for the support of the Répertoire International des Sources Musicales (RISM), a joint venture of the International Association of Music Libraries and the International Musicological Society. Projected to appear in 30 volumes, 18 of which have been published since 1960, RISM will inventory the sources held all over the world for the history of music to 1800. Another CLR-assisted work, the International Directory of Micrographic Equipment, was published by the International Micrographic Congress in 1967.

Several other grants have helped to make resources more readily available to users. The Association for Asian Studies received CLR funds in 1965 for the development of a Chinese Materials and Research Aids Service Center in Taipei, Taiwan. The center's purpose was to handle the republication of out-of-print scholarly materials, preparation of bibliographical research aids, acquisitions, and other services. In 1962 and again in 1967, Council grants made it possible for distinguished American librarians to conduct surveys and make recommendations relating to the development of research collections in Canadian universities. In 1963, the Council contributed to the cost of a survey of the use of the Dewey Decimal Classification outside of the United States. The study gave special attention to the necessity of adapting the classification tables locally to reflect more closely the literature, history, religion, and geography of individual countries, particularly in Africa and Asia.

The development of standards or agreements across national boundaries has been the objective of other CLR awards. A series of grants to the Music Library Association allowed that organization to send a key representative to participate in the deliberations of the International Cataloging Code Commission of the International Association of Music Libraries. The commission's discussions resulted in the approval in 1965 of international rules for the full cataloging of music. In 1964 the Pan American Union sought the assistance of the Council in preparing a standard list of subject headings in Spanish for the use of Latin American libraries in organizing collections and catalogs. The list, published in 1968, was freely distributed throughout Latin America and to library schools in the United States.

On two occasions the Council has provided support for attendance at the International Congress of Orientalists. The XXVII Congress, held at the University of Michigan in 1967, attracted nearly 2500 specialists. From the Council's point of view, an important feature was the inclusion of a panel of librarians. This gained the favorable attention of many scholars present and led to the formation of the International Association of Orientalist Librarians. The next congress met in Canberra in 1971, and there the association held a series of well-received library seminars. In both cases, grants from the Council made possible the attendance of a number of Asian librarians.

International Federation of Library Associations

In the last six years, however, the nature of the Council's support for international activities has altered. By 1970, it had become apparent that the most effective way to promote international cooperation among librarians and library systems was not through dispersed support for a

variety of projects to meet needs as they emerged. The consensus was that more could be achieved through assumption of a more aggressive leadership role by an organization in which many countries, including the United States, participated on an equal basis. The International Federation of Library Associations seemed the logical choice, for it already had consultative status in UNESCO and for many years had provided an international forum for the discussion of library problems. Moreover, after a period of self-examination IFLA had determined that its influence would be greatly increased by a permanent professional staff that could effectively carry forward and expand the ongoing activities of the organization. A decision had been made to revise its dues schedule on a gradual basis in order to gain the funds needed to accomplish this important goal.

In 1971 and again in 1974, CLR made grants that enabled IFLA to strengthen its administrative and staff operations while it restructured its dues schedule and moved toward self-support. By September 1975, IFLA reported that the new dues system had indeed helped to make administrative operations financially self-supporting and had also stimulated membership growth by over 153 percent. As of January 1975, 637 associations and libraries from 98 countries had joined the organization.

At the federation's forty-first General Council Meeting in Oslo in August 1975, a new organization plan was discussed. The plan calls for IFLA to undertake an active program of substantive work, supervised by a professional board. New professional divisions, sections, round tables, and working groups would be created, organized either by type of library, library function, or regional activities. Members and affiliates would register for participation in section work. In order to administer these activities, the existing secretariat would be expanded to include a professional unit, headed by a deputy secretary-general responsible to the

professional board for the coordination of program services and regional development. The unit would also serve as a clearinghouse on international library activities and related international offices.

To support the proposed expanded activities of the IFLA secretariat, the Council made a new grant of \$174,000 to cover the period of March 1, 1976, to December 31, 1978. During the first four months of the grant period, IFLA appointed a deputy secretary-general who will begin the task of developing the professional unit in July 1976. Final approval of the proposed structure is expected to be given at IFLA's August 1976 General Council Meeting in Lausanne, Switzerland.

Universal Bibliographic Control

One of IFLA's most important activities has remained the promotion of international cataloging agreements. At the aforementioned IFLA-sponsored meeting of cataloging specialists in Copenhagen in 1969, a proposal was developed for the establishment of a permanent secretariat for the IFLA Committee on Cataloguing in order to furnish needed continuity and coordination of its important work. In 1971, the Council awarded funds to IFLA for the secretariat, which has since engaged in a number of activities leading to major developments in the cataloging field. Among those activities is a publications program that includes definitive works on standards for international cataloging and the quarterly journal International Cataloguing. In 1973, the Cataloguing Committee secretariat presented a long-term program for developing a worldwide system for the exchange of bibliographic information -- a system based on the concept of Universal Bibliographic Control (UBC). The following year, the IFLA executive board approved a plan to make the realization of UBC a major goal of the Cataloguing Committee secretariat; the retitled IFLA International Office for

Universal Bibliographic Control includes as one of its functions the activities of the Cataloguing Committee.

As explained by Dorothy Anderson, UBC office director, in a recent article, "UBC envisages a system in which each country undertakes the responsibility of recording the publications (with that word used in its widest possible sense) produced in that country and makes those bibliographical records in accordance with standards which are internationally accepted and acceptable." In global terms, then, each publication would be cataloged only once, in the country of origin, and the bibliographic record thus produced would be used in information systems all over the world. In order for the record to be most useful, it must be made immediately after the publication is issued; this presupposes the establishment in each country of a coherent system of national bibliographic control.

Two Council grants covering the three-year period that ends June 30, 1977, have made it possible for the UBC office to carry forward its activities. The office also receives financial support from UNESCO and a number of national libraries. In addition to publishing International Cataloguing, the UBC office:

- Acts on suggestions for projects made by IFLA section and committees and other members of the library and information communities;
- Functions as a clearinghouse for information and as a coordinating, publishing, and consultative center;
- Sets up working groups, services them, and publishes the results of their work;
- Promotes standardization in the UBC area.

A major step forward in gaining acceptance of the concept of UBC occurred when the UNESCO Intergovernmental Conference on the Planning of National Documentation and Archives Infrastructures, held in Paris in September 1974, recommended that UBC be promoted by UNESCO in cooperation with IFLA as a major policy objective. Accordingly, through its NATIS (National Information System) Program, UNESCO is sponsoring a Conference of National Bibliographies to be held in the fall of 1977. The UBC office is closely involved with the preparation of this conference.

Other activities of the UBC office during the past year illustrate the nature of its work. For example, the office was given the primary responsibility for coordinating the planning of the IFLA World-Wide Seminar held in Seoul, Korea, from May 31 to June 5, 1976, and hosted by the Korean Library Association. UBC staff members chaired sessions, presented papers, and acted as rapporteurs for the seminar, the theme of which was "Library Resources and National Development: Use and Control of Eastern Publications by East and West." Over 400 librarians, half from outside Korea, attended the six-day event. Western libraries have recently shown increasing interest in acquiring Eastern publications for research purposes and to serve Asian communities in the West. With the progress of library development in Asia, this has highlighted the timeliness of this seminar's theme.

In another area, the UBC office surveyed national ISBN (International Standard Book Number) agencies located within national libraries. This was the first step in a joint project with the International ISBN Agency to determine current applications of the ISBN system in libraries and the possible adaptation of the ISBN for use in bibliographic records. The survey questionnaire asked the national agencies to explain current uses of ISBNs in such library processes as acquisitions, cataloging, circu-

lation, interlibrary loan, national and international bibliographic data exchange, mechanization, accounting, and stock control. The survey was completed during the year and a short summary published in the IFLA Journal, Vol. 2 (1976), No. 3, which stated, "The conclusions drawn by those colleagues who completed the questionnaires suggest that the most successful applications of the ISBN system are to be found in the fields of national and international data exchange, electronic data processing and interlending. The chief reasons given for lack of success in applying the ISBN to these processes are the percentage of material without ISBNs and inconsistency in citing ISBNs in published information and data interchange."

Perhaps the most significant area of UBC office activity is the development of standard formats for preparing bibliographic records to be exchanged in the universal system. The office coordinates the activities of a number of working groups concerned with various standard formats called International Standard Bibliographic Descriptions (ISBD). Recommended ISBDs for monographic publications and serials have already been published by the UBC office; in preparation are draft descriptions applying to nonbook materials and cartographic materials. A general ISBD is also under consideration for use by IFLA working groups in preparing these specialized formats and by librarians working on the compilation of cataloging codes. The IFLA Working Group on Content Designators, which has been developing a universal format to be used in the international exchange of machine-readable records (UNIMARC), has also reported progress. The UBC office will publish the text of the UNIMARC format as soon as final editorial work is complete. Other UBC publications during the past year covered such topics as the arrangement of entries for complex material under headings for personal authors, the use of corporate headings in library

catalogs and national bibliographies, and uniform titles for liturgical works of the Catholic church.

The IFLA Office for Universal Bibliographic Control is taking an active part in an international bibliographic network study, recommended and approved at a Paris meeting of national librarians in October 1975. A Council on Library Resources grant of \$11,000 to the Library of Congress enabled it to join with the national libraries of Australia, Canada, France, and Great Britain in funding the study. The UBC office has agreed to act as secretary and treasurer for the study and to participate in producing the bibliographic portion. This calls in part for an assessment of existing incompatibilities in records produced by various nations and possible future standards work. Other parts of the overall study will include an investigation of communications capabilities and requirements for the exchange of data on an international basis, an examination of the levels of information and organization required by such a system, and recommendations. A steering committee -- composed of representatives from the National Library of Canada, British Library, Library of Congress, Bibliothèque Nationale (France), Bibliothèque Royale (Belgium), Deutsche Bibliothek (Frankfort), Koninklijke Bibliotheek (Netherlands), Det Kongelige Bibliotek (Denmark), UNESCO, and the IFLA Office of Universal Bibliographic Control -- has been appointed to consider the final report and make recommendations.

International Council on Archives

The success of the enlarged IFLA secretariat and the activities of the Office of UBC encouraged the Council last year to make another grant of this type, this time for the purpose of strengthening the new secretariat

of the International Council on Archives (ICA). CLR's interest in the activities of this association began in 1966 when Council funds supported ICA's Extraordinary Congress and two resultant committees: one to facilitate scholarly access to archives, the second to study methods for the publication of archival sources. The new grant has made possible the addition to the secretariat staff of an executive assistant and a bilingual secretary. During the past year the secretariat engaged in numerous activities designed to foster the development of archives throughout the world. These included the formulation and translation of the agendas, working documents, and minutes of various international archival meetings; developmental missions to nations such as Ethiopia and Somalia in order to negotiate archival programs; and support services for new committees and sections within ICA. For several years the International Council on Archives has worked closely with UNESCO, IFLA, the Federation Internationale de Documentation (FID), and other international organizations in support of world archival needs.

ICA signed four contracts with UNESCO during the past year for completion of the following projects: preparation of a guide to the archives of international organizations; formulation in French and English of a list of archival terms as a first step to developing a glossary of archive terminology; preparation of an introduction to archivology intended for administrators, librarians, and documentalists; and formulation of a worldwide list of archival restoration workshops. In addition to income received from contracts and the sale of publications, ICA is supported by dues from member archives. During the grant period, ICA hopes to increase its revenues from these sources to the point where no outside financial help is

needed. The French National Archives houses the secretariat at no cost and West Germany's Federal Archives has provided additional staff.

Opportunities for International Exchange

While the Council's work in promoting international cooperation in the last few years has been largely through the activities of IFLA, its concern has been demonstrated in other ways as well. For example, because of the implications for libraries, the Council has followed with interest the work of the Federation Internationale de Documentation and has assisted several of its conferences and meetings. Support has also been given to other conferences, meetings, seminars, institutes, etc., of importance to librarians all over the world, such as the first and second U.S. - Japan Conferences on Libraries and Information Science in Higher Education, held in Japan in 1969 and in the United States in 1972. Two inter-American seminars received Council aid in 1973. The first dealt with integrating the information services of libraries, archives, and documentation centers in Latin America and the Caribbean, while the second concentrated on centralized cataloging and the use of MARCAL (MARC for Latin America). In 1974, a grant to the American Council on Education enabled its Task Force on Library and Information Resources of the Government/Academic International Education Interface Committee to hold an essential meeting with its advisors to discuss library services in support of international education.

From its inception, the Council has recognized that international cooperation will come about only through the efforts of individuals, motivated by their roles as representatives of organizations and by their personal desires to learn and apply new techniques of librarianship developed throughout the world. In the exchange of information across national boundaries, both U.S. and foreign librarians have significant roles to play,

for there must be cross-fertilization of ideas before mutually beneficial solutions to library problems can be reached. Accordingly, the Council has from time to time set aside small sums to help defray travel costs incurred by individuals who have assumed or been assigned leadership roles in international gatherings. Prior to making grants of this nature, CLR draws heavily on the advice and knowledge of outside consultants in appropriate related fields to ensure that those persons receiving support will have a significant impact in promoting international cooperation in librarianship. During the past year, several examples of this sort of activity took place. With Council aid, the U.S. branch of the International Association of Music Libraries (IAML) will be able to send a representative to the deliberations of the IAML Cataloging Commission in Norway in August 1976. Likewise, a small CLR grant allowed Dr. Saad M. el-Hagrassy, head of the Department of Library Science, Cairo University, to deliver an important paper on the translation, adaptation, and application of the ISBD(M) to Arabic publications at the IFLA World-Wide Seminar held in Seoul, Korea, in June 1976.

Occasionally, Council support provides opportunities to important library leaders to study in other lands developments in their particular fields of interest, thus promoting an international awareness of library programs and methods. A grant this fiscal year to Marc Chauveinc, director, National Bibliographic Center, Bibliothèque Nationale (Paris), enabled him to undertake a three-week study tour focusing on automation in U.S. libraries. In a similar vein, Professor William V. Jackson, an expert in Latin American library development, has received from the Council partial support of a study of library development, library education, and university libraries in Latin America, during his forthcoming sabbatical leave.

International Consultants

For the past eight years, the Council has been fortunate in having the benefit of the aid and advice of two widely respected and internationally prominent librarians. Upon his retirement as director of the British Museum, Sir Frank Francis, president of IFLA from 1964 to 1969, joined the Council for two years as a full-time resident consultant on international library matters. Although he returned to England in late 1970, he continues to assist CLR on both specific projects and more general matters of international library import. Dr. Herman Liebaers, president of IFLA from 1970 to 1974, has served the Council in a similar fashion, first as full-time resident consultant for one year, then as an advisor to CLR on matters relating to the world's libraries. Formerly the director of the Royal Library of Belgium, Dr. Liebaers now serves the King as Grand Marshal of the Royal Court of Belgium. These two world-renowned librarians have played an essential role in advising the Council on the most effective use of its funds for promoting cooperation and learning in the field of international librarianship.

Librarians, like professionals in many other disciplines, have become increasingly cosmopolitan in their outlook; they know that the effect of national decisions on international commitments can no longer be ignored. This viewpoint has the entire approval of the Council, which will continue to monitor events and support those activities that appear to contribute to the solution of library problems world-wide. In fiscal 1976, a total of \$187,109 was allocated for programs in this area of increasing importance.

Most of the Council's grants fall quite neatly into six or seven well-defined areas -- those that have been discussed so far in this report. Each year, however, the opportunity comes to provide assistance for helpful programs that cannot properly be said to belong in any of the established categories of activity. Some of these deal primarily with archives, which are institutions very closely related to libraries. Others have to do with surveys, publications, meetings, and a variety of matters that are important to libraries and those who use them. These are discussed in the pages that follow.

Assistance for Archival Programs

The Council's original charge drew attention to the need for coordination among archival programs, as well as among libraries. This report has mentioned several such CLR projects, the most current being assistance for the secretariat of the International Council on Archives discussed earlier in these pages. Two other leading archival organizations, the Society for American Archivists (SAA) and the U.S. National Archives and Records Service (NARS), have received CLR grants for projects to solve the special problems that face repositories of archives, records, and other specialized documents.

The earliest grant to the Society for American Archivists resulted in the major survey of state archives described in chapter I. The resulting document, published in 1964, stimulated the development of new state archival programs and the improvement of others. In 1967, another grant to the society enabled the author of the state survey, Dr. Ernst Posner, to conclude a study of ancient archival practices. Published by

Harvard University Press in 1972, Archives in the Ancient World was a co-winner of the SAA's 1973 Waldo Gifford Leland Prize. Patricia K. Grimsted was the other winner that year for her Archives and Manuscript Repositories in the USSR: Moscow and Leningrad (Princeton U. Press, 1972). In 1971, the Council and NEH had provided a matching grant to Dr. Grimsted for the preparation of a two-volume companion to her prize-winning study, also scheduled for publication by Princeton University Press. This work will provide a directory of archives and other manuscript repositories in the fifteen republics of the USSR, together with an annotated bibliography of published guides, catalogs, and other research aids. While continuing work on the manuscript, Dr. Grimsted has published interim reports as articles in The American Archivist and the AHA (American Historical Association) Newsletter.

Two other SAA projects received Council assistance in recent years. First, a small CLR grant enabled the society to publish in 1970 a Reader for Archives and Records Center Buildings, a compilation of articles relating to the planning and functional equipment for U.S. archives and records center buildings. Second, in 1970 SAA appointed a committee for the 1970s; with Council assistance, the committee reviewed the society's organizational structure, programs, and goals and developed a new long-range plan for meeting the needs of its members. The plan was presented to the membership in 1972, and many of its recommendations have since been put into effect.

In 1966, SAA joined with the American Historical Association and the Organization of American Historians in forming a committee to study the situation surrounding the integration of the U.S. National Archives and Records Service with the General Services Administration. NARS had

formerly been an independent agency, and its change in status led to widespread concern about its ability to function efficiently within the new framework. The Council assisted the study, out of which grew both a report with recommendations and a book-length account of the history and current situation of the Archives, entitled The Records of a Nation; Their Management, Preservation, and Use and written by the committee's secretary.

For the past ten years, NARS has been involved in another project, the use of computer technology to index existing finding aids for archival and manuscript materials and to create new ones. In 1967, NARS received a two-year CLR grant to test and improve the SPINDEX (Selective Permutation Indexing) program in order to make it as useful as possible to all archives. This program had been successfully applied by NARS several times, for example, to index the White House files of President John F. Kennedy.

In SPINDEX II, NARS undertook the creation of a new computer software package for use with collections of almost any size and with enough versatility to allow for the idiosyncrasies of differing collection descriptions. During the first year of the project, computer programs were written that could be used by any archival institution or manuscript depository to index materials held by one institution or to coordinate related materials held by different depositories. This is especially important in creating single indexes to varied collections, such as those held in the Presidential libraries.

In devising and testing SPINDEX II, NARS worked with other institutions to ensure that the program would provide compatibility. The cooperating institutions were Cornell University, the Library of Congress, the Minnesota Historical Society, the University of Alaska, the Smithsonian

Institution, the Ohio Historical Society, the State Historical Society of Wisconsin, and Wayne State University. The largest records files, however, are located in the National Archives, and it is there that most of the system implementation has taken place thus far. NARS has used SPINDEX II to produce an automated index to the Guide to Cartographic Records in the National Archives, to create a Catalog of National Archives Microfilm Publications, and to design finding aids and indexes to captured German records and the Papers of the Continental Congress. SPINDEX II, Report and Systems Documentation, published in 1975 by the National Archives and Records Service, provides a description of the project as well as a detailed guide to its application.

Archival collections frequently contain large quantities of nonbook materials that require special handling. These may be in the form of photographs, manuscripts, microforms, slides, etc. The Council has made several grants for the preparation of handbooks and manuals, of equal value to archives and libraries, that discuss methods of organizing, preserving, administering, and servicing materials in special formats. An example is Betty Jo Irvine's Slide Libraries: A Guide for Academic Institutions and Museums, published in 1974 by Libraries Unlimited. Two CLR grants to the American Association for State and Local History (AASLH) have aided in the preparation of works involving special collections. The first award, made in 1970, resulted in the 1975 publication of the 376-page Modern Manuscripts, written by Kenneth W. Duckett. Described by one reviewer as "an essential, if not indispensable, tool," the guide contains practical information on the management, care, and use of manuscript collections. In 1972 a second grant enabled AASLH to begin preparation of a manual dealing with photograph collections. Entitled The Collection, Use, and Care of Historical

Photographs, the volume will discuss the philosophy of photographic acquisition and the practical problems of establishing and maintaining a collection. It is scheduled for publication in November 1976.

Copyright and Libraries

The long copyright debate has also engaged the interest of the Council over the years. Although recently the efforts of Congress, publishers, librarians, and the National Commission on New Technological Uses of Copyrighted Works (CONTU) seem to have resolved many of the conflicts over the issue, for many years progress was uncertain. Verner Clapp, the first president of the Council on Library Resources, was a valiant and persuasive proponent of the interests of libraries in the debate. A widely recognized authority, he wrote several major essays on the subject of copyright and participated in national efforts to resolve the issue.

A 1959 Council grant to the New York Public Library on behalf of the Joint Libraries Committee on Fair Use in Photocopying provided funds for legal consultant fees in connection with the committee's investigation of problems faced by libraries in responding to requests for copies of publications. Then in 1963 a small grant was made to a nonprofit corporation concerned with problems affecting communication in science and education. The grant enabled the group to investigate the feasibility of a copyright clearinghouse which, it was hoped, would help to dissipate the logjam created by the conflicting interests of libraries and their users on the one hand and publishers and authors on the other. Another grant was made in 1967, this time to the American Library Association for support of studies by its Committee on Copyright Issues. While no direct grants

have been made since that time for projects dealing with copyright matters, the Council has attempted to follow events closely. An eminent librarian, who also serves as a CLR consultant, was appointed to serve on CONTU as a representative of copyright users. CONTU provides a forum for the expression of views and a mechanism for developing solutions to the complex issues that technological advances in computers and photocopy methods present to owners and users of works protected by copyright.

Standards for Library Statistics

When the Council began its work in the late 1950s, one problem needing attention concerned the incompatibility of library statistics. In 1961, for example, there were 156 major recurring statistical surveys in the United States, but using them for comparative purposes was difficult, if not impossible. The problem stemmed from a lack of agreement on the definitions of the most fundamental terms -- a book, library use, reference service, etc. Joining in efforts to rectify the situation, the Council provided funds for partial support of a study to develop standardized practices and terminology, sponsored jointly by the American Library Association, Special Libraries Association, American Standards Institute (now known as ANSI), Association of Research Libraries, and the U. S. Office of Education. The result was the publication in 1966 of a definitive work, Library Statistics: A Handbook of Concepts, Definitions, and Terminology, still used by statistical gathering agencies today.

On the international level, UNESCO faced a similar problem in its attempts to assemble library statistics for the countries of

the world. To encourage the development of international standards in this area, the Council provided funds for a series of meetings and conferences on the topic, sponsored by such interested organizations as the International Federation of Library Associations, the International Standards Organization, and the American Standards Institute. In 1970, a meeting of a Special Committee of Government Experts, convened by UNESCO and attended by 73 delegates from 43 countries, resulted in a document entitled The International Standardization of Library Statistics that contained a report of the conference, the working papers, and final recommendations. The report was used as the basis for a General Conference Recommendation for Library Statistics approved in November 1970, providing standard definitions and terminology for members of UNESCO to use in supplying data for UNESCO's national library statistical surveys.

Specialized Surveys and Status Reports

In addition to the efforts to provide standards for gathering library statistics, the Council has also furnished funds for specific surveys. In 1968 a Council grant of \$20,000 to the American Association of Law Libraries (AALL) initiated a project to collect and analyze important data concerning law libraries. Although the original proposal called for a comprehensive survey of all law libraries, it was found to be more practicable and useful to conduct separate surveys for four distinct groups -- law school libraries, libraries serving a local bar, governmental law libraries, and law firm libraries. The association also determined that data collection of this nature should be a continuous activity rather

than a one-time venture. Hence a new proposal was written, and in 1970 the original grant was revised and extended to June 30, 1975, to allow for the new (and improved) approach. During the five-year period, a number of surveys were conducted and the results published in the association's Law Library Journal. Especially notable were the results obtained from surveys of law school libraries, conducted annually with the cooperation of the American Bar Association and the Association of American Law Schools. The latest report of this survey, which appeared in the May 1976 issue of Law Library Journal, contains detailed information on the salaries, fringe benefits, and education of law school library staff, along with figures for the library's collection size, staff, expenditures, facilities, hours of operation, and use. AALL now plans to continue the annual survey of law school libraries and to conduct surveys in the other three categories on a triennial basis. To assist in this effort, the Council has agreed to extend the period of the grant to June 30, 1979, with no increase in funding.

Concern about the quality and economic welfare of the library profession was the stimulus for a series of CLR-funded salary surveys of college and university librarians. Donald F. Cameron and Peggy Heim prepared the first three surveys for the academic years 1969-70, 1970-71, 1972-73, which provided comparisons of the compensation structures of academic librarians and faculty members. A comparison was also made of the average compensation structure in various kinds of academic libraries (e.g., public university, private university, church-related college, etc.). The survey showed

as well the average compensation by library function.

In 1975, ALA's Association of College and Research Libraries successfully sought Council support to continue the series by collecting and publishing information on the salaries and fringe benefits of academic librarians for the 1975-76 academic year. In December 1975, questionnaires were mailed to all academic libraries in institutions participating in the American Association of University Professors salary survey. The analysis of the responses will attempt to show how much, if any, improvement has occurred in the economic status of librarians since the 1972-73 survey and how salaries of academic librarians compare with those of the classroom faculty. Data has also been collected on the number of women and minorities employed in academic libraries and their rates of compensation. The final report will be published in October 1976.

During the past year the Council supported another type of statistical study, this time concerning the nation's 34 historically black public colleges. The study was made under the direction of the Office for Advancement of Public Negro Colleges, a division of the National Association of State Universities and Land-Grant Colleges. By the end of June, responses to questionnaires were being analyzed to elicit comparative information on the size of collections, staffs, facilities, grants received, services to students, and interinstitutional cooperative arrangements. The final report is expected by the end of the summer.

University extension library services are the subject of another CLR-supported survey. Extension services have existed for

many years, yet they have received little attention and have generally not been coordinated with other library activities. Librarians in this field may have a particular knowledge of the needs of adult students in relation to nontraditional education. In the hope that publishing information about university extension library services will foster cooperative ventures with each other and with other types of libraries, the Council in 1971 awarded a small grant to Michigan State University to assist in the publication of a directory of university extension library services at institutions belonging to the National University Extension Association.

Since then, two editions of the directory have appeared. The second, dated June 1976 and entitled A Directory of Extension Library Services at N.U.E.A. Member Institutions, contains separate entries for 76 university extension libraries. In addition to the address and telephone number, each entry provides information on the area serviced by the library, staff, organization, collection, subjects emphasized, and budget. Work on the directories was conducted under the aegis of the ACRL/NUEA Joint Committee on University Extension Library Services.

Valerie Bloomfield reported to the Council in February 1976 that she had finished the information-gathering stage of her CLR-funded study of significant private research libraries in England. Since receiving the grant in late 1973, Mrs. Bloomfield has surveyed 50 libraries established by private initiative. Differing in the purposes for which they were founded and the sources from which they draw their support, the libraries fall into six broad institu-

tional categories: private foundations; missionary societies and religious denominations; literary, philosophical, and scientific societies; learned societies; special collections; and professional associations. The study is being conducted under the direction of CLR consultant Sir Frank Francis.

CLR-Supported Publications

Two books promising to be of substantial interest to library building planners have received recent Council assistance, and one is nearing completion. William S. Pierce, chief of facilities planning at Pennsylvania State University, used a six-month sabbatical leave during 1975-76 to complete the photography and text for a book tentatively entitled "Planning the Library Interior." Marcel Dekker, Inc. has contracted to publish the book, which Mr. Pierce expects to complete by September 30, 1976.

Ellsworth Mason, head, Special Collections Department, University of Colorado, received a small CLR grant in June 1976 to enable him to visit libraries in the United States and Canada in preparation for a book on library buildings. Dr. Mason, who has had wide experience as a library building consultant, plans to revise material previously published on the topic and to add new material, part of which will consist of critical building reviews. Scarecrow Press has agreed to publish the volume, tentatively entitled "Mason on Library Buildings."

Federal policy and library planning is the topic chosen by R. Kathleen Molz for a CLR-supported book based on her five-year experience as the chief planning officer for library programs at

the U.S. Office of Education. Now a member of the faculty at Columbia University, Dr. Molz has completed work on the manuscript, which has been accepted for publication as a unanimous choice of the M.I.T. Press' advisory board. The work will assist librarians who must deal with federal programs by increasing their knowledge of the ways federal officials make decisions on the planning, budgeting, and administration of legislated programs.

Because most of the grants in this category are small ones, a correspondingly small share of CLR funds is allotted to it. During the past fiscal year \$ 9,349 was awarded for projects of this kind.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

JULY 1, 1975 - JUNE 30, 1976

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JAMES A. TEW, Accountant

1

Until his resignation in May 1976.

2

Dr. Davis replaced Mr. Butterfield on his resignation.

3

Dr. Hard succeeded Dr. Wagman on November 8, 1975.

4

As of September 1975.

BOOKS AND ARTICLES RESULTING FROM COUNCIL GRANTS, 1975-76

	Page*
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COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
SCHEDULE OF APPROPRIATIONS FOR COUNCIL ADMINISTERED PROJECTS
JUNE 30, 1976

	Appropriations	Awards	Project Costs Paid	Appropriated Balance 6/30/76
Academic Library Development Program 1976-77	\$100,000	\$ 47,046	\$ 6,168	\$ 46,786
Continuation 1977-78	200,000			200,000
Academic Library Management Program 1974-77	60,000		40,840	19,160
Continuation 1977-78	110,000			110,000
Advanced Study Program 1977-78	110,000			110,000
Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control 1975	22,000		15,658	6,342
Continuation 1976	25,000			25,000
Computer Output Microfilm Study	20,000		5,244	14,756
Conversion of Serials - CONSER	17,198		6,601	10,597
Fellowship Program 1977-78	100,000			100,000
Library Service Enhancement Program 1976-77	220,000	193 399	12,373	14,228
Continuation 1977-78	210,000			210,000
Study of significant private libraries in England	10,000		6,979	3,021
Travel (foreign) by U.S. librarians for purposes important to profession	5,875	4,175		1,700
Travel (other) by U.S. librarians for purposes important to profession	3,000	1,027		1,973
Total				<u>\$873,563</u>

CLR-SUPPORTED PROJECTS ACTIVE IN FISCAL 1976

	Unpaid 6/30/75	FY 1976 Grants (Adjustments)	Payment (Refund)	Unpaid 6/30/76
AMERICAN ASSOCIATION FOR STATE AND LOCAL HISTORY, NASHVILLE, TENNESSEE				
Preparation of book on the collection, care, and use of photographs (\$10,000-1972)	\$ 5,500			\$ 5,500
Preparation of a manual on the collection and servicing of local history material in libraries (\$34,604-1970)	2,680	(\$1,121) ¹	\$ 1,559	-0-
AMERICAN ASSOCIATION OF LAW LIBRARIES, COMMITTEE ON STA- TISTICS, WASHINGTON, D.C.				
Survey of U.S. and Canadian law library resources (\$20,000-1968)	4,904		485	4,419
AMERICAN COUNCIL OF LEARNED SOCIETIES, NEW YORK CITY				
Survey of Arabic Manuscripts in Libraries and other re- positories in the U.S.		\$ 15,000	12,000	3,000
AMERICAN LIBRARY ASSOCIATION, CHICAGO, ILL.				
Consumers' Handbook for Public Libraries (\$8,372-1975)	4,372		2,000	2,372
Revision of <u>Anglo-American</u> <u>Cataloging Rules (AACR)</u> (\$111,431-1975)	61,431		12,000	49,431
Survey of Compensation Struc- tures of librarians in post- secondary education, 1975-76		6,894		6,894
AMERICAN SOCIETY FOR INFORMATION SCIENCE, WASHINGTON, D.C.				
Index to <u>JASIS</u> (\$19,910-1975)	9,910		9,910	-0-
ETTA ARNTZEN, ATHENS, GA.				
Revision of Guide to Art Refe- rence Books (\$8,000-1971)	1,600			1,600

	Unpaid 6/30/75	FY 1976 Grants (Adjustments)	Payment (Refund)	Unpaid 6/30/76
ASSOCIATION OF RESEARCH LIBRARIES, WASHINGTON, D.C.				
Office of University Library Management Studies (\$81,136-1974)	\$ 21,774		\$ 21,774	-0-
(\$210,000-1975)	210,000		60,000	\$ 150,000
W. J. BARROW RESEARCH LABORA- TORY, INC., RICHMOND, VA.				
Operation of a laboratory for investigations relative to the preservation of books and other library materials (\$240,000-1975)	117,278		93,793 (11,500)	34,985
BOSTON THEOLOGICAL INSTITUTE, CAMBRIDGE, MASS.				
ISSNs for theological serials(\$1,000-1975)	250	1,200	250	1,200
COLLEGE ENTRANCE EXAMINATION BOARD, NEW YORK				
CEEB Office of Library Inde- pendent Study Projects (\$50,000 1974)	25,000		24,493	507
		19,943	10,000	9,943
COLUMBIA UNIVERSITY, NEW YORK				
Support for Columbia University Library planning office (\$126,308-1972)	9,508	(6,702) ¹	2,806	-0-
COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS				
Academic Library Development Program (\$100,000-1975)	88,125	(5,293) ² (46,786) ³	22,000	14,046
Academic Library Management Intern Program (\$100,000-1974, \$265,000-1975)	243,561	(35,281) ²	77,895	130,385
Advanced Study Program (\$115,000-1975)	114,695	(9,695) ²	-0-	105,000
Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Con- trol (\$22,000-1975)	19,741	(19,741) ²	-0-	-0-

	Unpaid 6/30/75	FY 1976 Grants (Adjustments)	Payment (Refund)	Unpaid 6/30/76
COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS (cont'd)				
Conversion of Serials - CONSER (\$250,000-1975)	\$225,726	\$(11,459) ²	\$75,175	\$139,092
Fellowship Program thru Sept 1977	86,056	52,583 (22,449) ¹	54,360 (2,002)	63,832
S. M. al-Hagrassy, travel assistance		2,109	2,109	-0-
Joint CLR-NSF Conference on National Bibliographic Control (\$4,275-1974)	427	(427) ²	-0-	-0-
Library Service Enhancement Program		193,399	20,726	172,673
Microform Reader Testing Device (\$10,650-1973, \$4,000-1975)	4,166	(4,166) ²	-0-	-0-
Participants' expenses at two meetings on networking and standards		3,250	2,760	490
Participants' expenses at second networking meeting		2,750		2,750
Travel (foreign) by U.S. librarians for purposes important to profession	2,806	5,875 (1,700) ³	7,181 (200)	-0-
Travel (other) by U.S. librarians for purposes important to profession		1,027	1,027	-0-
Travel funds to enable selected foreign librarians to visit the U.S.	5,265		3,495 (141)	1,911
Study of significant private libraries in England (\$10,000-1974)	5,850	(5,850) ²	-0-	-0-
SUZANNE DODSON, UNIVERSITY OF BRITISH COLUMBIA, VANCOUVER				
Guide to Large Collections in Microform		1,950	500	1,450

	Unpaid 6/30/75	FY 1976 Grants (Adjustments)	Payment (Refund)	Unpaid 6/30/76
EARLHAM COLLEGE, RICHMOND, IND. Periodical list for <u>Choice</u> (\$7,500-1975)	\$ 5,200			\$ 5,200
EASTERN MICHIGAN UNIVERSITY, YPSILANTI, MICHIGAN Project LOEX (\$41,969-1975)	38,569		\$ 10,200	28,369
GOVERNORS STATE UNIVERSITY, PARK FOREST SOUTH, ILLINOIS Selective dissemination of micro- fiche documents - pilot project (\$5,138-1973)	938	(758) ¹	180	-0-
INTERNATIONAL COUNCIL ON ARCHIVES, WASHINGTON, D.C. ICA Secretariat (\$72,000-1975)	66,500		22,000	44,500
INTERNATIONAL FEDERATION OF LI- BRARY ASSOCIATIONS, THE HAGUE, HOLLAND IFLA General Secretariat (\$45,000-1974, \$45,000-1975)	26,444	(651) ¹	25,793	-0-
Professional Activities Sec- retariat		\$174,000	21,986	152,014
Universal Bibliographic Con- trol (\$70,000-1974, \$144,200- 1975)	150,200		68,000	82,200
WILLIAM V. JACKSON, NASHVILLE, TENNESSEE Study of Latin American libraries		1,445		1,445
DONALD M. JACOBS, BOSTON, MASS. Index of pre-Civil War Newspapers (\$500-1975)	100		100	-0-
LIBRARY OF CONGRESS, WASHINGTON, D.C. Feasibility study on LC as a national bibliographic center (\$94-632-1975) 67,632			54,000	13,632
Study of hardware and software needs (\$6,500-1975)	1,500	(27) ¹	1,473	-0-
National union catalog format study (\$5,000-1975)	3,000		3,000	-0-
International bibliographic net- work study		11,000	11,000	-0-
Integration of CONSER into national bibliographic services at LC		165,800	16,350	149,450

	Unpaid 6/30/75	FY 1976 Grants (Adjustments)	Payment (Refund)	Unpaid 6/30/7
LIBRARY OF CONGRESS (cont'd.) Microform Edition of Register of Additional Locations Data Base		\$ 12,200	\$ 10,200	\$ 2,000
MICHIGAN STATE UNIVERSITY, EAST LANSING, MICHIGAN University extension library services directory (\$1,609-1971)	\$ 402			402
R. KATHLEEN MOLZ, NEW YORK CITY Preparation of book on Federal policy and library planning (\$8,000-1975)	4,000		4,000	-0-
NATIONAL ASSOCIATION OF STATE UNI- VERSITIES AND LAND GRANT COLLEGES, ATLANTA, GEORGIA Status report on libraries of historically black public colleges		2,500	2,000	500
NATIONAL ENDOWMENT FOR THE HUMANITIES, WASHINGTON, D.C. Larger-scale development and applica- tion of morpholine process for pre- serving deteriorating books		88,000	88,000	-0-
Toward a California Library Automation Network		121,900	121,900	-0-
NATIONAL LIBRARY OF CANADA, OTTAWA To increase the library's ability to authenticate titles in CONSER		78,000		78,000
OHIO COLLEGE LIBRARY CENTER, COLUMBUS, OHIO Development of on-line acquisition subsystem (\$124,250-1975)	79,250		21,000	58,250
PTC RESEARCH FOUNDATION, CONCORD, N.H. Conference on abstracting legal ar- ticles for future computer storage and retrieval		5,250	3,000	2,250
PENNSYLVANIA STATE UNIVERSITY, UNIVERSITY PARK, PENNSYLVANIA Assessment of Impact of Management Review and Analysis Program (MRAP)		31,509	7,000	24,509
WILLIAM S. PIERCE, STATE COLLEGE, PA. "Planning the Library Interior" (\$3,000-1975)	3,000		2,500	500

	Unpaid 6/30/75	FY 1976 Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refund)	Unpaid 6/30/76
FRANK RODGERS, PORTLAND STATE UNIVERSITY, PORTLAND, OREGON Manual of British Government Publications		\$ 4,300	\$ 4,000	\$ 300
G. F. SHEPHERD, ITHACA, N.Y. Travel to meeting		163	163	-0-
SOUTHEASTERN LIBRARY NETWORK, ATLANTA, GEORGIA Training librarians to participate in SOLINET (\$10,000-1974)	\$ 3,400		2,200	1,200
STANFORD UNIVERSITY, PALO ALTO, CA. Toward a California library automation network (\$348,800-1975) (superseded by matching grant of \$121,900 to NEH for the purpose)	243,800	(243,800) ¹		-0-
SYRACUSE UNIVERSITY, SYRACUSE, N.Y. Improved access to books by augmentation of MARC records		76,615	25,000	51,615
UNIVERSITY OF CHICAGO, CHICAGO, ILL. Library data management system (\$350,000-1975)	250,000		150,000	100,000
Fellowship program for holders of non-library Ph.D. degrees (\$103,000-1974)	37,600		34,350	3,250
UNIVERSITY OF IOWA, IOWA CITY Conference on publication of American historical manuscripts (\$3,750-1975)	1,231	(405) ¹	826	-0-
UNIVERSITY OF ILLINOIS LAW LIBRARY, CHAMPAIGN, ILL. On-line computer reference service		1,080	750	330
UNIVERSITY OF NORTH CAROLINA, CHAPEL HILL, N.C. Administration of ANSI Committee Z-39 through April 1976 (\$14,000-1975)	11,000		9,290	1,710
Through June 1977		29,649		29,649
Through June 1978		23,719		23,719

	Unpaid 6/30/75	Grants (Adjustments)	FY 1976 Payments (Refund)	Unpaid 6/30/76
UNIVERSITY OF THE STATE OF NEW YORK ALBANY, N.Y. (for State Library) Study of state government information needs (\$25,000-1974)	\$ 4,000			\$ 4,000
VANDERBILT UNIVERSITY, FOR JOINT UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES, NASHVILLE, TENN. Establishment of a model research and development unit (\$171,107-1969, \$89,465-1072)	55,760		\$ 51,000	4,760
WABASH COLLEGE, CRAWFORDSVILLE, IND. For its College Library Program: matching grant (\$50,000-1970)	5,000		2,500	2,500
WASHINGTON UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES, ST. LOUIS, MISSOURI Development of a generalized procedure for the internal financial auditing of university libraries		\$ 10,000	4,000	6,000
WESTERN INTERSTATE COMMISSION FOR HIGHER EDUCATION, BOULDER, COLORADO Design and development of a western interstate bibliographic network (\$79,325-1975)	61,825		52,500	9,325
TOTALS	\$2,390,976	1,143,110 ¹	1,348,559	2,185,527
less adjustments/ refunds		(275,913) ² (91,912) ³ (48,486)	(1,843)	(402,468)
	\$2,390,976	\$ 726,799	\$1,334,716	\$1,783,059

1. To restore unused portion to fund balance.

2. Amount reflects the portion of the grant allocated for administrative costs which, prior to June 30, 1975, was included with total grant. Beginning with this report, project costs for Council-administered projects will appear separate from the grants payable schedule.

3. Amount reflects the portion of the grant appropriated for future awards; prior to June 30, 1975 this amount was included with total grant. Beginning with this report, appropriations for future awards will be included in the appropriated fund balance.